

D4.2 - COMPLETE GREEN ECONOMY MODEL (GEM)

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A series of system dynamics models have been developed to analyse the impacts of bio-based circular systems in key sectors like construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. These models assess environmental, social, and economic dimensions, capturing the complex relationships between factors such as material demand, consumption patterns, and life cycle impacts. Starting with drivers such as population dynamics, the models trace a material's journey through manufacturing, use, resale or reuse, recycling, and disposal, highlighting the role of energy consumption and the importance of resource efficiency. The models also focus on product management strategies, particularly the cascading use of bio-based materials, to promote sustainable resource utilisation. Each model is tailored to a specific region—Italy for textiles, the Netherlands for chemicals, and Germany for construction and plastics—allowing for detailed analysis and targeted policy development. In essence, these models serve as platforms for scenario simulations, exploring policy interventions that align with EU and regional sustainability goals.

This report presents model inputs for the simulation of three scenarios namely, Business as Usual (BAU), BioTransition, and BioRevolution, and offers full model documentation.

Across all industries, policies are categorized into demand-side initiatives, materials and energy efficiency improvements, material-switching strategies, and enhanced recycling efforts. In the construction industry, emphasis is placed on increasing building renovation rates, improving material efficiency, substituting cement with wood-based materials, and maximizing waste recycling to transform the sector into a carbon sink. The plastics industry focuses on reducing single-use plastics, boosting material efficiency, adopting bio-waste feedstocks, and significantly increasing recycling rates to lead the shift toward circularity. The textile sector targets extended product lifetime, improved energy efficiency, greater incorporation of bio-based materials, and robust waste collection and recycling systems to minimize environmental impact. Lastly, the chemicals industry aims to enhance both material and energy efficiency, increase the use of bio-based inputs, and improve waste management practices to achieve zero pollution and align with EU sustainability targets. Each scenario from BAU to BioRevolution represents a scaling up in the ambition of the intervention options, reflecting increasing levels of commitment towards achieving a sustainable and circular bio-based economy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

A series of system dynamics models have been developed to comprehensively analyse the multifaceted impacts of bio-based circular systems within key sectors like construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. These models are analytical tools that evaluate the environmental, social, and economic dimensions inherent in these industries.

The models are designed to delineate the intricate interplay between various factors shaping material demand, consumption patterns, and subsequent life cycles. Starting from the fundamental drivers of population dynamics and material consumption, the models traverse the entire spectrum of a material's life cycle. This includes its utilisation, potential resale or reuse, recycling prospects, and ultimate disposition, whether in landfills or through alternative pathways.

Energy consumption entailed in material production is integral to these models, accentuating the significance of resource efficiency and end-of-life management practices. A pivotal focus lies on product management strategies, particularly the cascading utilisation of bio-based materials, underscoring the imperative of sustainable resource utilisation.

Each industry model serves as a bespoke case study, tailored to specific geographic locales. The textile industry model is designated for Italy, the chemicals industry model for the Netherlands, and both the construction and plastics industry models for Germany. This localized approach facilitates nuanced analysis and targeted policy formulation. These industry models serve as dynamic platforms for scenarios, enabling the exploration of diverse policy interventions in isolation or conjunction with national and regional objectives. The envisaged scenarios aim to elucidate potential pathways for sustainable transition, aligning with overarching policy targets at both EU and regional scales.

Drawing insights from policy workshops, two overarching scenarios emerge for the selected countries: the "BioTransition" and the "BioRevolution." The former underscores incremental progress, adhering to established policy frameworks and existing objectives. Conversely, the latter advocates for a paradigm shift towards a fully circular bio-based economy, characterized by ambitious and innovative policy goals, accelerating the pace of transition.

In summary, these industry models and policy variable analyses offer actionable insights and pathways toward a more resilient and regenerative future, constituting a robust framework for navigating the complexities of sustainable development within key industrial sectors.

2 SCENARIOS AND ASSUMPTIONS

This section provides details about the scenarios modelled, the policies included in each scenario for each industry sector, and the assumptions on the policy inputs in the model.

There are three scenarios considered. The baseline scenario is the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario, which assumes that the current trends continue in the future with no ambition of a circular bio-based economy (CBBE). The BioTransition scenario emphasizes transition aspects and status quo policy objectives with a focus on implemented, existing policy goals towards a circular bio-based economy. The BioRevolution scenario integrates new and more ambitious goals, aiming at a rapid transformation towards a fully circular bio-based economy.

The scenarios operationalized consider the portfolio policy scenarios for each industry (i.e. construction, plastics, textile and chemicals) carried out in the SUSTRACK D4.1. For each industry, there are specific policies and hence policy inputs. The policies are organized into four main categories, namely policies for the demand side, materials and energy efficiency policies, materials switching policies, and recycling policies.

Additionally, an EU-level scenario was introduced to show the interplay between the biobased scenarios per industry and the overall targets/policies of the EU in the area of a biobased circular economy. The EU scenario is an extension of the Bio-Revolution scenario to the national level, covering additional areas of interventions in different sectors. The intention is to show the potential and consequences of a national circular biobased plan and the interaction between industry and national planning.

To that end, three scenarios were developed, the first is a scenario that accounts for the current directives and targets of the EU in terms of the biobased circular economy. The second scenario increases the biofuel transport mix to show how increased biomass demand will cause higher demand for agricultural land. The last scenario introduces electrification of transport to reduce the amount of biofuels required, creating a synergy with land use.

2.1 Construction industry

In the construction industry, six policies are outlined and categorized into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as shown in Table 1. For this Industry, there is a distinct focus on increasing the use of biobased products to shift from being a carbon source to becoming a carbon sink, based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 49 and Table 50). The goal is to boost both raw material productivity and the utilisation of secondary materials to enhance the circularity of material flows and decrease reliance on non-abiotic resources.

In relation to the demand policies, the increase in the annual share of building renovation policy aims to renovate 2% of the buildings by 2030 and 4% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario, and a higher ambition as assumed for the BioRevolution scenario, being the renovation rate 3% by 2030 and 6% by 2050. These shares are established based on the policies in the Biotransition scenario (see Table 46) that propose “At least 2% of annual energy renovation in buildings” (European Commission, 2020) and “(...) renovate 3% of their buildings’ floor space annually” (European Commission, 2021) by 2030. As the model is focused on the building construction process and not the building energy use, the policy was reinterpreted as the increase in the building renovation rate, resulting in efficiency improvement.

For the efficiency policies category, the increase in material efficiency policy is set up for the BioTransition scenario to be 1.5% per year by 2030 and 1% per year by 2050, for the BioRevolution scenario the ambition increases to 2% per year by 2030 and 1% per year by 2050. These policy inputs come from the policy goals (see Table 46) “Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year” for the BioTransition scenario and “Improve materials productivity at 2% per year” for the BioRevolution scenario (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020). The goal was adapted to be accomplished in 2030 for the BioTransition scenario and then the ambition increased for the BioRevolution scenario, following the nature of this last scenario. The decrease of the rate to 1% in the long term for both scenarios corresponds to a reality assumption that the material efficiency in the construction sector can have limitations.

The material switching policy for wood-based materials instead of cement is thanks to the policy goal “(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink” (European Commission, 2021) and the other policy goal is “climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use” (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019). The policy input, the share of cement replaced by wood, has been established by the modelling team as there is a lack of a numerical indication for such goals. For the BioTransition scenario, the share is to be 15% in 2030 and 30% in 2050, and for the BioRevolution scenario is to be 20% by 2030 and 40% by 2050.

Finally, for the recycling policies category, the three interventions about waste collection, recycled materials and reused materials are based on the next set of policies from D4.1 (see Table 46):

- “The preparing for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled” (European Commission, 2023).
- Article 11 (2a) “(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;” (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008).
- “The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 80% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 50%” (European Commission, 2023).
- “The use of primary raw material in buildings renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 90% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 75%” (European Commission, 2023).

These policy goals indicate mostly inputs for material recycling preparation and secondary raw materials use. As they are not indicating directly the shares of waste to be collected, recycled and reused, the modelling team has reinterpreted the values provided in light of the BAU shares and established the next values:

- The share of waste collection increases from 70% by 2024 to 100% by 2045 in the BioTransition scenario, and increases to 100% a bit earlier (by 2040) in the BioRevolution scenario.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 70% by 2024 to 90% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario, and increases to 95% by 2050 in the BioRevolution scenario. The fact that the share does not increase to 100% in any scenario provides a realistic perspective of the material flows, as not all waste can be recycled.

- The share of waste for reuse or to be resold decreases from 15% by 2024 to 5% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario, and to 2.5% by the same year in the BioRevolution scenario as a result of the increase in the recycling rate. The rest of the share goes to the landfill.

Table 1. Scenario's assumptions for a circular biobased economy in the construction industry - Germany

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	BioTransition scenario	BioRevolution scenario
Demand (Buildings renovation)	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 2%/year 2050 -> 4%/year	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 3%/year 2050 -> 6%/year
Efficiency (Improve materials productivity)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 1.0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 2.0%/year 2050 -> 1.0%/year
Switching (Wood-based materials)	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 20% 2050 -> 40%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 70% 2050 -> 70% Share or materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2050 -> 70% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 80% 2045 -> 100% Share or materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 70% 2040 -> 82% 2050 -> 90% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 85% 2040 -> 100% Share or materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 78% 2040 -> 88% 2050 -> 95% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16%

	2024 -> 15% 2050 -> 15%	2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 15% 2040 -> 9% 2050 -> 5%	2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 11% 2040 -> 6% 2050 -> 2.5%
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2.2 Plastics industry

In the plastics industry, seven policies are detailed and classified into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as depicted in

Table 2. These policies aim to raise ambition and underscore the significance of the sector for the circular economy. Accelerating the transition to alternative feedstocks, refining recycling quotas, and specifying content quotas for non-fossil-based materials could serve as a model for other sectors, leading the path toward a circular, biobased economy. The policy inputs used are based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 51 and Table 52).

Regarding the demand policies for the plastic industry, they are designed to decrease or discourage the demand for plastics in the future. The first policy is the ban on single-use plastics, which will bring a reduction in plastic product consumption. The policy input for the model is the percentage of demand reduction, which for the BioTransition scenario will be an 8% reduction by 2030 and 15% by 2040; and for the BioRevolution scenario, the percentage reduction is 10% by 2030 and 20% by 2040. The policy is included due to the next policy goal: “Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic” (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019). As the policy goal does not suggest a numerical policy input, the modelling team has assumed the percentages considering that there will be a smooth transition for the plastics demand decrease. The second demand-related policy is the percentage decrease in plastic demand by 1,5% from 2030 onwards in the BioRevolution scenario, which corresponds directly to the policy goal for Germany that suggests an annual reduction in the growth of plastic of 1,5 %/year (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018). This goal has not been established and hence not modeled for the BioTransition scenario.

For the efficiency policies category, the increase in material efficiency policy is set up for the BioTransition scenario to be 1.5% per year from 2025 and for the BioRevolution scenario, the ambition increases to 2% per year from 2025. These policy inputs come from the policy goals for Germany: “Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year” for the BioTransition scenario and “Improve materials productivity at 2% per year” for the BioRevolution scenario (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020). The goal was established from 2025 on, for the plastic industry as the material efficiency for plastics has the potential to evolve fast due to technology in manufacturing processes and material types.

In the case of material switching policies, the model uses the share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste as a policy input, assuming for the BioTransition scenario a share of 14% by 2030 and 26% by 2040, and for the BioRevolution scenario the same shares for earlier years: 14% by 2028 and 26% by 2035. These shares have been set up considering the next policies portfolio while at the same time adjusting the shares to a smooth transition for material consumption.

- Use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact-sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023).

- From 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).
- From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact-sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).
- From 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).
- Article 7: From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact-sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact-sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single-use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single-use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 50 % for contact-sensitive plastic packaging, except single-use plastic beverage bottles; (b) 65 % for single-use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil-based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilisation).

It is important to notice that the policy portfolio states the shares for recycled materials for specific plastic product categories (e.g. non-contact sensitive packing). Nevertheless, the ballpark values used for creating the shares are 35% by 2028 and 65% by 2040. As packing plastics share among all plastics is around 40% (European Environment Agency, 2023), when 35% is applied to the 40% results in 14% and when 65% is applied to the 40% results in 26%.

Lastly, the recycling policies have been established as next:

- The share of waste collection will increase from 73% by 2024 to 90% by 2050 for both the BioTransition and BioRevolution scenarios.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 55% by 2024 to 80% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario, and increases to 95% by 2050 in the BioRevolution scenario. The fact that the share does not increase to 100% in any scenario provides a realistic perspective of the material flows, as not all plastic waste can be recycled.
- The share of waste for reuse or to be resold decreases from 15% by 2024 to 1.5% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario, and to 4.8% by the same year in the BioRevolution scenario as a result of the increase in the recycling rate. The rest of the share goes to the landfill. For instance, in the BioRevolution scenario, only 0.2% of the plastic waste will go to the landfill.

These policy inputs are set up based on the following inputs. It is important to notice that the shares are not used directly as they point in general to a more specific subset of plastic products, which is packing products. As the model uses aggregated values, we adapt the shares to total

plastic products while being consistent with a smooth and feasible pathway for the collection, recycling and reuse quotas, considering the BAU values.

- “Member states shall set up a separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass” (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018).
- “By 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- “By 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Increase recycling quota for plastics by 2025: 3,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
- “Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 7,5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040” (European Commission, 2023).
- “Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets
 - (c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated;
 - (d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 60 % of plastic; (ii) 35 % of wood” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Increase recycling quota for plastics by 2030: 8,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
- Mechanical recycling 45% and chemical recycling of 15%. Adapted from Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany (2021) & Transition Agenda - Circular Economy (2018).
- Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil-based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilisation).

Table 2. Scenario's assumptions for a circular biobased economy in the plastics industry - Germany

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	BioTransition scenario	BioRevolution scenario
Demand (Ban of products and demand decrease)	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2040 -> 0%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 8%/year 2040 -> 15%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 10%/year 2040 -> 20%/year
	Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2040 -> 0%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 15%/year 2050 -> 15%/year
Efficiency (Improve)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency:	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency:	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency:

materials productivity)	2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 1.5%/year	2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 2%/year 2050 -> 2%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 14% 2040 -> 26%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2028 -> 14% 2035 -> 26%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 73% 2050 -> 73% Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2050 -> 55% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 11% 2050 -> 11%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 90% Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2030 -> 59% 2050 -> 80% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 1.5%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 90% Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2030 -> 62% 2050 -> 95% Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 9% 2050 -> 4.8%

2.3 Textile industry

In the textile industry, six policies are detailed and classified into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as illustrated in Table 3. The industry emphasizes the importance of waste stream separation to enhance resource efficiency by minimizing waste and disposal, based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 53 and Table 54). Setting specific quantitative targets for incorporating recycled products and sustainable textiles into value chains further supports the sector's transformation.

In the textile industry, the demand policy is focused on the lifetime of the products. In the BioTransition scenario, product lifetimes extend from 3.6 years in 2024 to 4 years by 2030 and 4.5 years by 2050. In the BioRevolution scenario, product lifetimes similarly start at 3.6 years in 2024, increasing more significantly to 4.2 years by 2030 and reaching 5 years by 2050. This policy is inspired by the next policy portfolio and modelled considering the materials and product flows of the model that can support such portfolio:

- “Establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects” (European Commission, 2022).

- “To support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products” (European Commission, 2022).
- “The strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts” (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).

Regarding efficiency policies, the policy modelled is focused on energy efficiency as a way to account for the policy goal: “(...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO₂ in the non-ETS sectors” (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022). The BioTransition scenario shows no annual increase in energy efficiency by 2024, then improves by 1% annually by 2030, and slows to a 0.5% increase per year by 2040. The BioRevolution scenario mirrors this pattern initially, with no increase in 2024, a 1% annual improvement by 2030 and results in 0.8% annual increase by 2040. As the policy goal is general for the energy sector in Italy, the modelling of the energy efficiency policy has been set up by the modelling team based on experience and feasible energy efficiency pathways.

For switching to bio-based materials, both scenarios start with 0% of material consumption being replaced by bio-based materials in 2024. By 2030, the BioTransition scenario achieves a 10% replacement, growing to 20% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario is more ambitious, reaching a 15% replacement by 2030 and 30% by 2050. For this policy input, the baseline policy goals are focused on eco-designs and bio-based fibres, such as:

- “establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects” (European Commission, 2022).
- The adapted or added policy goal: supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer).
- The adapted or added policy goal: The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%.
- Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycle and 20% will be sustainable textiles.

Finally, the recycling policies have been set up as follows:

- The share of waste collection for the BioTransition Scenario will increase from 10% by 2024 to 40% by 2030 and 80% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario starts the same but aims for 100% waste collection by 2050.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 10% by 2024 to 40% by 2050 in the BioTransition scenario and increases to 70% by 2050 in the BioRevolution scenario.
- The share of materials to be resold or reused in the BioTransition scenario is 5% in 2024, 10% by 2030, and 20% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario aims higher, with 5% in 2024, 15% by 2030, and 30% by 2050. The rest of the share goes to the landfill.

These policy inputs are set up based on the following inputs, considering feasible shares that are correspondent to the current situation (BAU):

- Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
- Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through “Textile Hubs” (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).

- Adapted or added policy goal: 30% of resources, materials and products placed on the textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 10% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused after collection.
- Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycle and 20% will be sustainable textiles.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 50% of resources, materials and products placed on the market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 15% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused in the after collection.
- Adapted or added policy goal: Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion.
- The development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).
- Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017).
- Adapted or added policy goal: Full circular textile material flows.

Table 3. Scenario's assumptions for a circular biobased economy in the textile industry - Italy

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	BioTransition scenario	BioRevolution scenario
Demand (Extension of product lifetime)	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 3.6 years 2050 -> 3.6 years	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 4 years 2050 -> 4.5 years	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 4.2 years 2050 -> 5 years
Efficiency (Improve in energy efficiency)	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.5%/year	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.8%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%

Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 10%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 80%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 100%
	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2050 -> 10%	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 20% 2050 -> 40%	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 50% 2050 -> 70%
	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2050 -> 5%	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%

2.4 Chemical industry

In the chemicals industry, six policies are outlined and categorized into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as depicted in Table 4. The industry aims for higher proportions of non-fossil-based carbon in material flows as a primary objective, as portrayed in the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 55 and Table 56). This aligns with achieving the zero-pollution target sooner, reducing concerning substances in recycled materials, and meeting overarching EU-level goals.

Initially, the chemical sector envisages both energy and materials efficiency. In the case of material efficiency, in the BioTransition scenario, there is an improvement of 1% annual increase by 2030 and a 0.5% increase by 2050. In the BioRevolution scenario, material efficiency shows a 1.5% annual increase by 2025 and then a 0.5% increase by 2050. The policy is modelled based on the next policy portfolio:

- reducing the raw material footprint coupled with a reduction of the environmental impact in 50% by 2030 (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).
- reducing the raw material footprint coupled with a reduction of the environmental impact in 75% by 2050 (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).

The energy efficiency policy shows the same pattern for annual improvement rate as the materials efficiency policy. This policy is modelled as a result of the general policy goals for emissions reduction and pollution: Reduction of 5 Mt of CO₂ emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021) & 0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020).

For switching to bio-based materials, both scenarios start with 0% of material consumption being replaced by bio-based materials in 2024. By 2030, the BioTransition scenario achieves a 10% replacement, growing to 20% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario is more ambitious, reaching a 15% replacement by 2030 and 30% by 2050. This policy is inspired by the policy goal: “Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50%” (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).

The recycling policies around waste collection, recycling and reuse, are based on the general policy goals: “To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimized” (European Commission, 2020) & “In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular” (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023). As the policy goals lack detail on collection, recycling and reuse quotas, the modelling team has made the next assumptions:

- The percentage of waste collection in the BioTransition scenario is 60% in 2024, increasing to 75% by 2030 and 90% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario starts the same but aims for 80% by 2030 and 95% by 2050.
- The share of materials to be recycled in the BioTransition scenario is 16% in 2024, rising to 30% by 2030 and 60% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario increases recycling to 40% by 2030 and 75% by 2050.
- The share of materials to be resold or reused in the BioTransition scenario is 1.92% in 2024, 15% by 2030, and 35% by 2050. The BioRevolution scenario aims for 15% by 2030 and 25% by 2050, starting at 1.92% in 2024.

Table 4. Scenario's assumptions for a circular biobased economy in the chemicals industry - Netherlands

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	BioTransition scenario	BioRevolution scenario
Demand			
Efficiency (Improve materials and energy efficiency)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.5%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%
Recycling (Material)	Percentage of waste collection:	Percentage of waste collection:	Percentage of waste collection:

recycling at the end of life)	2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 60% 2050 -> 60%	2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 75% 2050 -> 90%	2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 95%
	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 16% 2030 -> 16% 2050 -> 16%	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 16% 2030 -> 30% 2050 -> 60%	Share or materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 16% 2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 75%
	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 1.92% 2050 -> 1.92%	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 35%	Share or materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 25%

2.5 National Scenarios

In the following section, we delve into the assumptions underlying the national scenarios, which are crucial for understanding the pathways each country might take towards achieving sustainability goals. These assumptions provide the foundation for analyzing how different levels of biobased products and practices adoption, electrification, and industrial innovation could shape the future energy and economic landscape at the national level. By exploring these scenarios, we gain insights into the potential impacts and trade-offs associated with varying degrees of commitment to the CBBE across different countries. The scenarios introduce a switch to renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and biomass), increased use of biofuels in the transport sector, reduction in waste, and higher value addition from the specific national industry under the BioRevolution scenario.

2.5.1 Germany

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario, the power generation capacity in Germany mainly relies on coal and wind power. To simulate the shift towards more biobased technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar and wind are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios.

Table 5. Power Generation shares in Germany

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	2.22%	BAU: 2.22% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0.00%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	16.2%	BAU: 16.2% EUBB: 0%
Coal	29.7%	BAU: 29.7%

		EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	11.7%	BAU: 11.7% EUBB: 11.5%
Biomass	7%	BAU: 7% EUBB: 13%
Hydropower Large Scale	4.2%	BAU: 4.2% EUBB: 13%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Solar Large Scale	8.4%	BAU: 8.4% EUBB: 22.4%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	15.3%	BAU: 15.3% EUBB: 32.3%
Wind offshore	4.1%	BAU: 4.1% EUBB: 4.1%
Waste Generation	1%	BAU: 4.1% EUBB: 4.1%
Geothermal	0.04%	BAU: 0.04% EUBB: 0.04%

Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, Germany's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the European Union's biobased scenario, which emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Germany's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national-level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport sector, focusing on the transition to using more biofuels instead of the traditional petroleum-based products. In the EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use, sets 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU

biobased low transport) scenario is to have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels by 2030. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and biobased transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

2.5.2 Italy

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario, the power generation capacity in Italy mainly relies on Gas turbines (50% in 2022). To simulate the shift towards more biobased technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar, wind, and hydro are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios.

Table 6. Power Generation shares in Italy

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	3.7%	BAU: 3.7% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	49.8%	BAU: 49.8% EUBB: 0%
Coal	5.5%	BAU: 5.5% EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Biomass	5.8%	BAU: 5.8% EUBB: 15.8%
Hydropower Large Scale	16.4%	BAU: 16.4% EUBB: 50.4%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Solar Large Scale	8.7%	BAU: 8.7% EUBB: 21%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	7.2%	BAU: 7.2% EUBB: 10.4%
Wind offshore	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Waste Generation	0.8%	BAU: 0.8% EUBB: 0.8%

Geothermal	2.1%	BAU: 2.1% EUBB: 2.1%
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Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, Italy's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the EU biobased scenario, which emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Italy's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national-level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport section, focusing on the transition to using more biofuels instead of traditional petroleum. The EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use, sets that 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU biobased low transport) scenario is to have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels by 2030. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and biobased transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

2.5.3 Netherlands

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario, the power generation capacity in the Netherlands mainly relies on Gas turbines (50% in 2022). To simulate the shift towards more biobased technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar, wind, and hydro are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios.

Table 7. Power Generation shares in the Netherlands

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	3.15%	BAU: 3.15% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	46.37%	BAU: 46.37% EUBB: 0%
Coal	14.21%	BAU: 14.21% EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	3.13%	BAU: 3.13% EUBB: 0%
Biomass	7.1%	BAU: 7.1% EUBB: 12%
Hydropower Large Scale	0.07%	BAU: 0.07% EUBB: 3%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Solar Large Scale	9.41%	BAU: 9.41% EUBB: 40.41%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	8.2%	BAU: 8.2% EUBB: 36.23%
Wind offshore	6.51%	BAU: 6.51% EUBB: 6.51%
Waste Generation	1.8%	BAU: 1.8% EUBB: 1.8%
Geothermal	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%

Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, the Netherlands's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the EU biobased scenario, which

emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Italy's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national-level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport section, focusing on the transition to using more biofuels instead of traditional petroleum. The EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use sets that 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU biobased low transport) scenario is to have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels by 2030. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and biobased transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

3 DOCUMENTATION OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY MODEL

This model offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the materials lifecycle and energy dynamics within the construction sector. By initializing the model with the demand for housing, driven by population dynamics and per capita housing preferences, it accurately reflects the real-world scenario. The subsequent analysis of construction materials consumption, particularly cement, provides insights into resource utilisation and potential areas for optimisation.

Furthermore, the model's incorporation of lifecycle considerations, including reuse, recycling, and disposal of construction materials, adds depth to the analysis. By integrating considerations of policy-induced changes, the model can forecast employment generation within the construction industry, thereby providing stakeholders with valuable insights into the economic impacts of various policy interventions. Moreover, the model delves into the energy consumption dynamics inherent in the construction sector, shedding light on the sources and magnitudes of emissions associated with energy utilisation. By dissecting energy consumption across various sources such as natural gas, oil, electricity, renewables, and biofuels, the model enables stakeholders to identify potential areas for mitigation strategies and transitions towards greener alternatives.

3.1 Demand & Housing Stock

The estimation of demand for housing is used to determine the amount of construction materials required based on the average m² per person (see Figure 1). The demand serves as the primary driver in the model, providing input to the other components of the model. Without the need for housing, the energy, recycling, and employment structures would not only fail to increase but would instead diminish towards zero.

Figure 1: Causes tree Housing Demand

The demand for housing is driven exogenously by the average m² per person, with the data specifically and population forecasts for Germany (UN Population Division, 2022).

$$\text{desired building stock} = \text{users} * \text{average m2 per person}$$

The model uses a stock and flow structure, with the inflow representing construction and the outflow being the demolition of housing. The stock represents the number of buildings that are operational and in use. The desired building stock drives demand for buildings, which is calculated based on the desired building stock and the number of houses being commissioned, using a MAX function to prevent it from becoming negative.

$$\text{demand for buildings} = \text{max}(0, \text{desired building stock} + \text{decommissioning})$$

The building stock increases through construction and decreases through decommissioning. The lifetime of buildings, which determines the decommissioning rate, is initially set to 35 years. This duration illustrates that despite buildings having longer lifetimes, certain aspects may require repair earlier. The following assumptions, presented in Table 8, are used to calculate demand and to check its validity. Among the policies or interventions considered in the model, one relates to the lifetime of buildings, which can be extended via retrofits. Hence, the policy is represented through extending the building's lifetime.

Table 8. Parameters used in the demand model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Initial Lifetime	35	(Madhumitha, 2024)
Lifetime CBBE	Annual increase of 1.5%	Assumption
Average m ² per person	47	(Destatis, 2018)
m ² per dwelling	93	(Destatis, 2018)
Building Stock Value (2022)	43,336,000	(Destatis, 2022)

3.2 Material Consumption

Material consumption is estimated based on the construction rate. It reflects the amount of material that is required for new construction in any given year. The material consumed in prior construction can be recycled and reused, reducing the virgin materials used. In addition, if waste is generated during the construction process, some of the materials used will be stored in buildings, while others will be sent to landfill (if recycling is not possible) and disposed of.

The material consumption per sqm, labelled material consumption per unit in the model, decides the material consumed depending on scenarios. The equation thus, is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{material consumption per unit=} \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE(CEMENT TO WOOD switch=1:AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=1,} \\
 & \text{material consumption per unit CBBE(Time)*material consumption cement to wood CBBE,} \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE(CEMENT TO WOOD switch=0 :AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=1,} \\
 & \text{material consumption per unit CBBE(Time),} \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE(CEMENT TO WOOD switch=1 :AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=0,} \\
 & \text{material consumption per unit BAU*material consumption cement to wood CBBE,} \\
 & \text{material consumption per unit BAU)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

The IF THEN ELSE statement dictates, depending on which switch is active, the material consumption. If the “cement to wood switch” and the “material efficiency switch” are turned on (=1), the model will be impacted by various policy interventions. When the former switch is activated, cement demand will decline, and more wood will be consumed. If the latter switch is

activated cement will still be used, but in lower quantity. The logic allows for the interventions to be combined, thus, creating 4 possible scenarios, including the business-as-usual. The variable values and sources used in the material consumption per unit are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Parameters used in the material consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Material Consumption per unit BAU	1.91	(Karina & Annette, 2022)
Material Consumption per unit CBBE	A 1.5% annual increase in efficiency	Scenario
Material Consumption per unit cement to wood CBBE	0.5	

Recycled or reused materials are fed back into the material consumption process, reducing the demand for virgin materials. However, a minimum value of 0.1 is set for this variable to prevent it from becoming zero or negative. This reflects the fact that the model only considers virgin materials.

$$\text{Material consumption} = \max(0.1, \text{construction} * \text{material consumption per unit-products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse-delay material recycling and reuse-domestic reuse of construction materials})$$

The production waste from the construction of the buildings can be reused in later developments (Osmani, 2011). The equation for material recycling and reuse thus accounts for the percentage of waste able to be used and the amount of waste from that percentage that is actually reused.

$$\text{Material recycling and reuse} = \text{"end of life materials (waste)" * IF THEN ELSE(MATERIAL RECYCLING AND REUSE switch=0, share of material recycling and reuse BAU, share of material recycling and reuse(Time))}$$

The equation represents the management of recycling and reuse within an industrial context. It assesses the proportion of materials recycled or reused based on specific conditions. The "IF THEN ELSE" statement evaluates whether material recycling and reuse are active (represented by the "MATERIAL RECYCLING AND REUSE switch"). If the switch is set to zero, the model assumes a baseline scenario (BAU) and uses the predetermined share of recycling and reuse. Otherwise, it considers the increased share of production material to be reused. The assumptions and sources are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Parameters used in the material recycling model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of material that is waste	30%	(Osmani, 2011)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	48%	(Osmani, 2011)
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	The materials that go to waste in the construction process are materials that are not easily recyclable. Hence, the policy would slowly increase by 0.05% annually. Reaching 70% by 2100.	

3.3 Recycling and Reusing

Decommissioning and construction activities influence the recycling infrastructure within the model by contributing to waste streams. This waste is collected and diverted for either landfilling, recycling, or reuse. Consequently, these activities increase the inflow of materials into the recycling system's stockpiles. Table 11 shows the inflows and outflows for each stock modelled in this section.

Table 11. Overview of stocks and flows for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Product waste generated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste generated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected
Product waste collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse Products materials to landfill Products resold and reused
Landfill material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product materials to landfill Production materials to landfill 	None

As more buildings are decommissioned, the stock of product waste generated increases, which in turn increases the stock of product waste collected. The stock of product waste collected is then decreased through three outflows that either dismantle the materials for recycling, send them into the stock of landfill, or become resold. The material that is sent out from the recycling and reusing flows goes back to the material consumption equations to reduce the use of virgin materials. An overview of the structure can be found in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Stock and Flow Diagram for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Lastly, the variables that decide the share of materials being recycled etc. are presented in Table 12 with their sources and values. Alongside them are also their policy scenario counterparts to demonstrate the decided-upon aspirations. The BAU and CBBE scenarios can be individually controlled for greater exploration of the possible simulation space in the model.

Table 12. Parameters used for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	70%	(BMUV, ND)
Share of products collected CBBE	A 1.5% annual increase	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	68% in 2012	(Deloitte, 2015)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	A 2.8% annual increase since 2022	(European Environment Agency, 2022b)
Fraction resold and reused BAU	Landfill and recycling compose 72% of Construction and demolition waste, we are therefore assuming the rest is resold or reused.	(Deloitte, 2015)

<p>Fraction resold and reused CBBE</p>	<p>In the CBBE scenario the recycling rate increases till 90% leaving 10% to either be resold or to be landfilled. The assumption is that half of it always goes to landfill.</p>	
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3.4 Employment

The employment sector calculates the level of employment under each task using an exogenous “person per product” formulation. This formulation means that if the scenarios increase the recycling or building flows, the employment is endogenously calculated. An example of the equation is as follows:

$$\text{Employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

The more products that are resold and reused the larger the total employment for product repair and reuse is. Table 13 presents the values and sources for the employment equations. The units are person per product.

Table 13. Parameters used for the employment model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per m ²	0.2	Calculated
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	X	
Employment per unit collected and sorted	X	
Employment per unit recycled	X	
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit of waste landfilled	x	
Employment per unit of water consumed	x	
Employment per unit of energy consumed	x	

3.5 Energy Consumption

The industry requires energy to run the tools and machines, and for materials to be consumed. In the model energy consumption is determined by energy intensities and material consumption. Higher material consumption correlates with increased energy consumption, dependent on the constant energy intensity per source. Total fuel consumption is the sum of all energy consumed in TJ.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total fuel consumption} = \\ \text{renewables and biofuel consumption} + \text{oil and petroleum consumption} \\ + \text{natural gas consumption} + \text{electricity consumption in TJ} \end{aligned}$$

Using the energy consumption per type of energy, and corresponding emission factor determines the total CO₂e emission in tons for the industry.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total CO}_2\text{e emissions in tons} = \\ (\text{fuel renewable and biofuel emissions} + \text{fuel electricity emissions} + \text{fuel oil and petroleum emissions} \\ + \text{fuel natural gas emissions}) / \text{kg to ton} \end{aligned}$$

The energy intensities presented in Table 7 were calculated using the data for the total m² constructed in 2022 and the associated energy consumption.

Table 14. Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.000244684 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	4.65907e-005 gWh/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum Intensity	0.000543392 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Renewables and Biofuel Intensity	2.45456e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

3.6 Energy Prices

The associated costs of energy in the industry are a detriment to sustainable transitions with the higher prices for renewables. To inform the cost-benefit analysis of the scenarios, the price of energy is used to see the various annual costs associated with any policy decisions. The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price from the data that is closest to 2022. The value and source can be found in Table 15.

Table 15. Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	9.71809e-005 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	0.1512 Euro/kWh	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Oil and Petroleum Price	32.5461 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Renewables and Biofuel Price	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(Statista Research Department, 2024)

3.7 Material Costs

One of the methods of reducing emissions and increasing the circularity of an industry is to shift towards more sustainable materials. In the construction sector, this could be a shift towards wood instead of cement. These different materials have different costs and thus, the model accounts for the shift. Table 16 displays the source and value of said costs per m² of construction.

Table 16. Material costs used in the construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Costs per sqm in Cement Scenario	X	
Costs per sqm in Wood Scenario	X	

3.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of new construction and value addition per m². Two variations of the value addition per m² are calculated, one for conventional construction and one for biobased construction. The module only considers the value addition from new construction, and not secondary markets, such as real estate or market speculation.

Figure 3: Cause tree for Value addition in the construction sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Destatis, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$\text{Value addition intensity} = \frac{\text{Value addition}_t}{\text{Production}_t}$$

The forecasts for value addition are then in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the construction value addition, this is 0.66% growth annually. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top of it from the literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature data ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future biobased value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Germany, and thus, the construction sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 2.6% (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Value addition conventional and biobased for Germany's construction industry

The value addition or construction GDP is then the sum of the value addition, new construction, and share of the industry that is biobased, which is dependent on the policy levers active during the simulation. Taking the share of new production that is biobased and the counterfactual

provides a value addition that accounts for both. The equation is the sum of new construction and conventional value addition, accounting for the share that is biobased added to the share of construction value addition that is biobased.

$$\text{Real value added new purchases construction industry} = ((\text{construction} * \text{value added per virgin product construction} * (1 - \text{share of construction products manufactured using biobased products})) + (\text{construction} * \text{value added per virgin biobased material construction} * (\text{share of construction products manufactured using biobased products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}$$

Since the construction GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real construction GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 5: Use tree for real GDP construction industry

4 DOCUMENTATION OF THE PLASTIC INDUSTRY MODEL

This model is a comprehensive framework for analyzing the lifecycle of materials in the plastics sector in Germany. It starts with the initialisation of demand based on per capita plastic usage and total population figures, providing a realistic picture of the demand for plastic products. The model gives insights into the materials consumption dynamics within the industry.

Moreover, the model offers a lifecycle analysis that covers the reuse, recycling, and disposal of plastic products, providing a nuanced understanding of resource utilisation and waste management practices. The model also takes into account employment generation within the plastics industry and the potential impacts of policy interventions such as measures to promote recycling or reduce single-use plastics. This allows stakeholders to evaluate the socio-economic implications of different strategies. Additionally, the model considers the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions associated with the plastics industry, categorized by sources such as natural gas, heat, and electricity. This provides valuable insights into the environmental footprint of plastic production processes.

4.1 Plastic Demand

The demand for plastic is driven by consumption and thus, the two can be equated. To calculate demand in the model a static value for plastic consumption per capita is used and multiplied by the data and population forecast for Germany (UN Population Division, 2022). This provides a simple forecast of plastic demand in the future. In the BAU scenario, the plastic consumption per capita is set to 160kg derived from tons of plastic produced and the German population (Görlitz, 2018).

$$\text{Plastic consumption} = \text{users} * \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{REDUCTION PC USE switch} = 0, \text{plastic consumption per capita BAU}, \text{plastic consumption per capita (Time)})$$

The logic statement allows for policy scenarios to be run with different plastic consumption per capita. In this case, represents a ban on certain plastic packaging causing a reduction in plastic consumption. The policy values can be found in Table 17.

Plastic consumption drives the demand for the industry which affects the stock of product stock in use. The stock increases through the product purchase and decreases through product discard. The stock represents all plastic and does not disaggregate between the different products. The outflow is determined by an adjustment time set as 10 years in the BAU scenario and the CBBE scenario is a table function.

$$\text{product discard} = \text{Product stock in use} / \text{product lifetime}$$

The values and sources for the policy for plastic consumption and products in use can be seen in Table 17.

Table 17. Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Plastic Consumption per capita BAU	0.16	(Görlitz, 2018)
Plastic Consumption per capita CBBE	2023= 0.16; 2030= 0.12; 2050= 0.4	
Initial product lifetime	10	(Madhumitha, 2024)
Product lifetime scenario	2023= 10; 2030= 20	

4.2 Material Consumption

Material consumption is the amount of material consumed during the production of a plastic product. In the model, material consumption is driven by purchases to determine the number of materials needed, the recycled waste from previous productions, and recycled materials from discarded products. Recycled plastics reduce material consumption as they are not new in the system, hence the subtraction of recycled materials. The variable material consumption is only concerned with virgin plastics.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit} - \text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} - \text{delay material recycling and reuse}$$

Material consumption refers to the overall utilisation of materials within the system, encompassing both the acquisition of new materials and the reuse of existing ones. This is calculated by multiplying the quantity of products purchased by the amount of material consumed per unit of product, and then subtracting the materials recycled and reused. Some of the material that is consumed during production can be recycled which is determined by the following equation:

$$\text{material recycling and reuse} = \text{"end of life materials (waste)" * IF THEN ELSE(PRODUCTION MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=0, share of material recycling and reuse BAU, share of material recycling and reuse(Time))}$$

The equation considers both the share of material designated as waste and the proportion of material suitable for recycling to determine the materials available for reuse within the system. The switch enables toggling between the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario and the policy scenario.

To calculate the material consumed per unit the model uses an exogenous material consumption per unit variable that determines how many tons of input materials are needed for one ton of plastic products.

material consumption per unit=
IF THEN ELSE("BIO-BASED PLASTICS switch"=1 :AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=1,
*biobased material consumption per unit CBBE*material efficiency increase CBBE,*
IF THEN ELSE("BIO-BASED PLASTICS switch"=1, biobased material consumption per unit CBBE,
*IF THEN ELSE(MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=1, material consumption per unit BAU*material efficiency*
increase CBBE,material consumption per unit BAU)))

The logic statement is designed to facilitate multiple policy tests, including overlapping policies such as increasing material efficiency and introducing bio-based plastics. These policies are aimed at reducing material consumption, emissions, and waste concurrently. The values of the parameters and sources can be found in Table 18.

Table 18. Parameters used for the material consumption model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of Material that is waste	50%	(Gravgård, Kristensen, Svantesson, & Urhammer, 2021)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	9%	(United Nations Development Programme, 2023)
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=9%; 2030=11%; 2050=15%	
Material Consumption per Unit BAU	1.4 tons/product	
Biobased material consumption per unit CBBE	1	
Material efficiency increase CBBE	1	
Product lifetime scenario	Baseline: 10 Policy: Increases to 20 by 2030	

4.3 Recycling and Reuse

The waste generated during production and discarded plastic products in Germany is collected by waste collectors and subsequently sorted into recycling, reuse, and landfill categories. The model structure mirrors this behaviour, as waste from production and any product in use eventually enters the waste management system. Table 19 presents a summary of the three stocks used in this section and their respective inflows and outflows.

Table 19. Overview of stocks and flows for recycling model component, plastics industry model

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Product waste generated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste generated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected
Product waste collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse Products materials to landfill Products resold and reused
Landfill material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product materials to landfill Production materials to landfill 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials to incineration

Initially, the discarded products enter the stock of product waste generated where it is then transferred to the stock of product waste collected determined by the share of products collected. From the stock of product waste collected, there are three possible paths: reuse and resold, recycling, and landfill. If the plastic ends up in a landfill there is a possibility it is incinerated.

The flows are dictated by the recycling and reusing rates, with the remaining plastics that are not reused or recycled being directed to the landfill. To determine the landfill rate, the equation accounts for the inflow and then subtracts the sum of the other two outflows. This means that if there is a 100% recycling and reusing rate, there should be no materials flowing into the landfill stock. The materials that are recycled and reused flow back into the material consumption and plastic demand respectively.

$$\text{materials (products) landfilled} = \text{product waste collection} - (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} + \text{products resold and reused})$$

The recycling, reusing, incineration, and collection rates are determined by data and the policy scenarios are based on country aspirations. The values can be found in Table 20.

Table 20. Parameters used for the material recycling and reuse model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	73%	(European Environment Agency, 2022a)
Share of products collected CBBE	2023=73%; 2030=80%; 2050=90%	
Fraction resold and reused BAU	11%	(Herrman, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)

Fraction resold and reused CBBE	30% of plastics that is not recycled in CBBE scenario	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	55%	(Eurostat, 2023a)
Share of materials to incineration	50%	(Herrman, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)
Fraction of sorted plastic sold domestically BAU	5%	(Herrman, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)
Fraction of sorted plastic sold domestically CBBE	2023=5%; 2030=10%; 2050=20%	

4.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The model tracks downstream employment such as the employment per recycling material etc. One example of the equations is as follows:

$$\text{Employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This equation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton. All values for the different types of employment can be found in Table 21.

Table 21. Parameters used for the employment model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	x	
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit collected and sorted	x	
Employment per unit recycled	x	

Employment per unit of material repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit of waste landfilled	x	
Employment per unit of water consumed	x	
Employment per unit of energy consumed	x	
Employment per unit of waste incinerated	x	

The tree diagram presented in Figure 6 shows the different sources of employment in the plastics industry but also in all the industries (construction, chemicals, and textiles).

Figure 6: Sources of employment in the plastics industry

4.5 Energy Consumption

The plastic industry's main share of power comes from electricity, natural gas, heat, and other energy sources (Destatis, 2017). Using calculated energy intensities, the model converts the material consumption into energy consumption to endogenously calculate the emission from the

industry. Figure 7 shows the cause tree for the electricity formulation as all other equations follow the same structure.

Figure 7: Cause tree for electricity emissions from plastic production, plastics industry model

The sum of the emissions is used to calculate the total CO₂e emissions from the German plastic industry. Regarding fuel costs, the equation takes the 2022 price of electricity in the country and multiplies it by the energy consumption to find the annual energy cost. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment.

The energy intensities were calculated by dividing the annual energy consumption, in TJ, with the tons produced given the following values in TJ/ton except for the electricity intensity which is in kWh/ton (see Table 22).

Table 22. Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.002145	(Destatis, 2017)
Heat Intensity	0.000331154	(Destatis, 2017)
Electricity Intensity	1100.09	(Destatis, 2017)
Other Energy Source	0.000208769	(Destatis, 2017)

4.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in

Table 23. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating the same values are used for both prices.

Table 23. Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	0.0269947 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	0.1513 Euro/kWh	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Heat Price	1.3176e-006 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Other Energy Sources	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(Statista Research Department, 2024)

4.7 Material Costs

One policy aimed at reducing plastic usage involves transitioning to biobased plastics to enhance the industry's sustainability. However, producing biobased plastics incurs distinct costs, particularly when examined at an aggregate level. In other words, categorizing all plastics as "plastic products" does not accurately reflect the varied costs associated with producing biobased plastics. The price per ton of plastics is detailed in Table 24. The costs are measured in Euro/ton.

Table 24. Material costs used in the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Costs per ton of plastic	1000	(CAP ECO Recycling, ND)
Costs per ton of biobased plastics	X	

4.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of new plastic purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for biobased production. The module only considers the value addition from purchases, including reused plastics.

Figure 8: Cause tree for Value addition in the plastic sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Görlitz, 2018; UN Population Division, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$Value\ addition\ intensity = \frac{Value\ addition_t}{Production_t}$$

The forecasts for value addition are then in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the plastics value addition this is 0.66% growth annually. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top of it from the literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature data ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future biobased value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Germany, and thus, the plastics sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 2.6% (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Value addition conventional and biobased for Germany's plastic industry

The GDP of the plastics industry is calculated by summing the value addition, plastic purchases, and the biobased share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the biobased value addition, we consider the share of new production that is biobased along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both biobased and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of plastic purchases, conventional value addition, and the biobased shares of both plastic purchases and biobased value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of biobased and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{real value added new purchases plastics industry=} \\
 & ((\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin product} * (1 - \text{share of plastics products manufactured using} \\
 & \text{biobased products})) + (\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin biobased material} * (\text{share of plastics} \\
 & \text{products manufactured using biobased products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the plastics GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real plastic GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 10: Use tree for real GDP plastic industry

5 DOCUMENTATION OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY MODEL

This model offers a comprehensive analysis of the life cycle of materials used in the textile sector in Italy. It begins by calculating the demand for textiles based on the per capita consumption and total population of the country. This allows for a precise understanding of the dynamics of material consumption in the industry, with a particular focus on textile fibres as the primary component.

The model also incorporates a life cycle analysis that covers the use and disposal of textile fibres, reflecting a circular approach that promotes sustainability and resource efficiency. It takes into account the employment generated within the textile industry and the potential impacts of policy interventions, such as measures to promote textile recycling or reduce textile waste. This enables stakeholders to evaluate the socio-economic implications of different strategies.

Furthermore, the model also considers the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions associated with textile production processes, categorized by sources such as natural gas, oil and petroleum, renewables, heat, and electricity. This provides valuable insights into the environmental footprint of the industry.

5.1 Textile Demand

The Italian textile sector is a major industry in the country and reached 8 billion euros in sales in 2022 (Industria Italiana, 2023). The per capita consumption was calculated based on total sales in euros divided by price in euros to get the kilograms of textile produced. This is then divided by the population of Italy to get the ton/person value for per capita consumption (see Table 25). The consumption for Italian textiles is then calculated using data and a population forecast for Italy and the per capita consumption (UN Population Division, 2022). To find the consumption of new textiles, the following equation is used:

$$\text{consumption of new textiles} = \max(0, \text{textile consumption} - \text{reuse of textile in products}) / \text{relative product lifetime}$$

The subtraction of reused textiles is performed to avoid double-counting in the product purchase flow. Consequently, the variable only addresses new textiles, ensuring that the inflow to the stock of product stock in use includes reintroduced reused textiles back into circulation.

$$\text{product purchase} = \max(0, (\text{consumption of new textiles} + \text{reuse of textile in products}))$$

The stock of “product stock in use” represents the ton of textiles being used within Italy overtime. It increases through inflow, product purchase and decreases through the outflow, product discard. The product discard is the stock divided by adjustment time which can be altered depending on the scenario currently being simulated.

Table 25. Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Sales in 2022	8,100,000,000 Euro	(Industria Italiana, 2023)

KG price	0.57 Euro/kg	(European Environment Agency, 2023)
Product Lifetime BAU	3.6 Years	(Manshoven, et al., 2019)
Product Lifetime CBBE	2023=3.6; 2030=4.6; 2050=5	

5.2 Material Consumption

To produce textiles, raw materials such as fibre, cotton, and water are used. The material consumption in the model is calculated using the product purchases as a proxy for production, material consumption per unit, and accounts for recycled materials.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit} - \text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} - \text{delay material recycling and reuse}$$

This equation calculates the total consumption of virgin materials. It multiplies "product purchase" by "material consumption per unit." Recycled materials are excluded here because their environmental impact, including energy costs, has already been accounted for elsewhere in the model.

The recycled materials come from prior textile production waste that can be reused. The material consumption per unit is based on the exogenous input, "material consumption per unit" which is measured in tons of materials consumed per ton of material produced.

$$\text{material consumption per unit} = \text{IF THEN ELSE (MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \text{material consumption per unit CBBE (Time), material consumption per unit BAU)$$

The larger the material consumption per unit is, the more materials will be needed to produce the same amount of textiles. Thus, the higher the material consumption per unit, the lower the material efficiency is. This variable also determines the water and energy consumed by the production process. The parameters and their sources are provided in Table 26.

Table 26. Parameters used for the material consumption model component, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of Material that is waste	11%	(ConSORIZO italiano Implementazione Detox, 2022)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	46%	(ConSORIZO italiano Implementazione Detox, 2022)

Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=46%; 2030=60%; 2050=80%	
Material Consumption per Unit BAU	1	
Biobased material consumption per unit CBBE	2023= 1; 2030= 1; 2050= 1	
Water Consumption per Unit	352.113 Litre/Ton	
Energy Consumption per Unit	0.00287732 TJ/ton	Calculated
Energy Carbon Intensity	26.2 TonCO ₂ e/TJ	(Normand, 2023)

5.3 Recycling and Reuse

After textiles have been used on average for 3.6 years, the model routes the products into the recycling structure. This structure calculates waste generated and waste collected, determining the subsequent destination for the waste, the options being reused as is, recycled into fibres, or landfilled. The material flow is determined by rates that control the in and outflows of the structure and the values under scenarios can be seen in Table 27.

The “products resold and reused” outflow drives the domestic reuse of textiles as the percentage that is resold domestically is sent back to product purchases. The products that are dismantled reduce material consumption since the fibres do not need to be reproduced. Lastly, the materials that are landfilled are either sent to be incinerated or left in landfills. The stock of landfills is also affected by production waste. Since only a small part of landfills are ever properly disposed of, the share of materials that are incinerated remains low.

The rates for the in and out-flows were determined through the use of national-level data or proxies when such data was not available. Table 27 shows the values of the parameters and their source.

Table 27. Recycling, Reusing, and Landfill Rates for Italy, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	10%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Share of products collected CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=50%;2050=100%	

Fraction resold and reused BAU	5%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=45%;2050=100%	
Fraction of sorted textiles sold domestically BAU	40%	(Janmark, Magnus, Strand, Langguth, & Hedrich, 2022)
Fraction of sorted textiles sold domestically CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=45%;2050=55%	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	10%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=20%;2050=50%	
Share of Materials to incineration	80%	(Graham, 2020)

5.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the downstream level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The equations are as follows:

$$\text{employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This equation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton of X. All values for the different types of employment can be found in Table 28.

Table 28. Parameters used for the employment model component, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	x	
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	x	

Employment per unit collected and sorted	x	
Employment per unit recycled	x	
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit of waste landfilled	x	
Employment per unit of water consumed	x	
Employment per unit of energy consumed	x	
Employment per unit of waste incinerated	x	

5.5 Energy Consumption

The Italian textile industry is powered by a variety of different energy sources. The model structure calculates energy consumption per source using the associated energy intensities from the year 2022. The structure proceeds to use the energy consumption with the associated emission factor to calculate the emissions per source (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Causes tree for total CO₂e emissions from textile production, textile industry model

The sum of the emissions is then used to calculate the total CO₂e emissions from the textile industry. Regarding fuel costs, the equation takes the 2022 price of energy in the country and multiplies it by the energy consumption to find the annual energy cost. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment.

The energy intensities were produced by dividing the ton of textile produced in 2022 by energy consumption per energy source in the same year. The energy intensities can be found in Table 29.

Table 29. Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.00150493 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Heat Intensity	1.5e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	0.000344084 GWH/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum	9.60563e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Renewables Intensity	2.26761e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

5.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price with the data selected as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in Table 30. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating, the same values are used for both prices. Italy's renewable energy primarily comes from solar and hydro sources, predominantly utilized for electricity production. Consequently, the prices for both sources are generally the same.

Table 30. Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	3.1752e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Heat Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Oil and Petroleum Price	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Renewable Energy Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)

5.7 Material Costs

The costs of materials are contingent upon the input materials utilized. Given that the model assesses the textile industry at an aggregate level, the cost of materials is averaged to euros per ton of textile produced. However, the cost of materials would vary if the policy's share of recycled fibres increased. The following equation was utilized to compute the cost of materials, considering the proportion of recycled fibres used.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Annual Industry Cost for Materials} \\ & = (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} * \text{Cost of Recycled Fibers}) \\ & + (\text{Cost of Input Materials} * \text{material consumption}) \end{aligned}$$

The parameters used for the equation can be found in Table 31.

Table 31. Material costs used in the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Cost of Recycled Fibers	x	
Cost of Input Materials	x	

5.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of textile purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for biobased production. The module considers the value addition from purchases, including reused textiles, but does not disaggregate between the two.

Figure 12: Cause tree for Value addition in the textile sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Industria Italiana, 2023; European Environment Agency, 2023; Manshoven, et al., 2019) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$\text{Value addition intensity} = \frac{\text{Value addition}_t}{\text{Production}_t}$$

The forecasts for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the textile value addition this is 0.83% growth annually from 2028 onwards. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top of it from the literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature data ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future biobased value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Italy, and thus, the textile sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 5% (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Value addition conventional and biobased for Italy's textile industry

The GDP of the textile industry is calculated by summing the value addition, new purchases, and the biobased share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the biobased value addition, we consider the share of new production that is biobased along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both biobased and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of textile purchases, conventional value addition, and the biobased shares of both textile purchases and value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of biobased and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{real value added new purchases textile industry=} \\
 & ((\text{product purchase} \times \text{value added per virgin product} \times (1 - \text{share of textile products manufactured using} \\
 & \text{biobased products})) + (\text{product purchase} \times \text{value added per virgin biobased material} \times (\text{share of textile} \\
 & \text{products manufactured using biobased products}))) \times \text{COVID shock on capital}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the textile GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real textile GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 14: Use tree for real GDP textile industry

6 DOCUMENTATION OF THE CHEMICALS INDUSTRY MODEL

The chemicals industry model for the Netherlands offers a comprehensive analysis of the intricate nexus between population dynamics, chemicals demand, materials lifecycle, energy consumption, and CO₂ emissions within the chemicals sector. The model starts by analyzing the chemicals demand per capita and the total population of the country and then assesses material consumption patterns focusing on chemicals as raw materials. The model promotes a circular approach that includes stages such as use, reuse, recycling, and disposal, providing valuable insights into sustainable resource utilisation practices within the chemicals industry. This approach supports the overarching goal of fostering a circular economy. The model also considers employment generation within the chemicals industry itself and as a result of policy interventions, offering a holistic perspective on the economic impacts of various strategies and initiatives.

Furthermore, the model addresses energy consumption and CO₂ emissions associated with the chemicals industry from various sources such as natural gas, oil, waste, heat, and electricity. This provides a nuanced understanding of the environmental footprint of the sector and guides efforts towards emission reduction and the adoption of cleaner energy sources in alignment with the Netherlands' sustainability goals.

6.1 Chemical Demand

Chemical production predominantly serves the business-to-business (B2B) sector, emphasizing industrial demand. Consequently, the utilisation of per capita consumption may introduce inaccuracies in the model. However, it serves as a useful proxy to align total production with demand due to the limited availability of data regarding industrial demand. The chemical consumption equation is thus derived from the UN data and population forecast for the Netherlands and a calculated per capita consumption (UN Population Division, 2022).

$$\text{chemicals consumption} = \text{users} * \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{CONSUMPTION switch}=0, \text{chemicals consumption per capita BAU}, \text{chemicals consumption per capita CBBE}(\text{Time}))$$

The logic statement allows for policy interventions between the normal per capita consumption and the CBBE scenario where industrial use of chemicals is reduced in favour of more sustainable options.

The product purchase represents the total purchasing of chemicals in the Netherlands and serves as a proxy for production. It is calculated with the consumption of new chemicals (derived from per capita consumption) and the share of chemicals being reused domestically.

$$\text{product purchase} = \text{max}(0, (\text{consumption of new chemicals} + \text{reuse of chemicals}))$$

The product purchase inflow increases the stock of products in use, which is decreased by the outflow of product discard. The outflow is determined by an adjustment time representing the average lifetime of a chemical product. The lifetime of chemicals can vary from months to decades and thus, a compromise is to use the shelf life of reagents (ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020). The parameters used in the demand structure can be found in Table 32.

Table 32. Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Per capita consumption BAU	1.72 ton/person	(cefic, 2023) & (Eurostat, 2023b)
Per capita consumption CBBE	2023=1.72; 2030=1.65; 2050=1.5	
Product lifetime BAU	1.7 Years	(ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020)
Product lifetime CBBE	2023=1.7; 2030=2; 2050: 5	

6.2 Material Consumption

The input in the chemical production process are reactants and initial materials that start a chemical reaction to produce the desired chemical. The variation in material efficiency based on which chemicals are being produced introduced complexities with working on an aggregate level. Hence, the parameters are calibrated with the most common chemical in mind, sulfuric acid. The values for all parameters can be found in Table 33.

With material consumption based on sulfuric acid, the equation for the variable is determined by a ton of input materials to produce a ton of chemicals. Under the CBBE scenario, the material efficiency is increased due to a transition to less biomass consumption.

$$\text{Material consumption per unit} = \text{IF THEN ELSE}(\text{MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \text{material consumption per unit CBBE}(\text{Time}) * \text{material consumption per unit BAU}, \text{material consumption per unit BAU})$$

The material consumption requires energy and water to be produced which is determined by the energy and water consumption per unit (see Table 33). The shift from carbon-intensive fuels to more renewable sources for direct energy use would reduce the carbon intensity from production (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Cause tree for CO₂e Emissions from Direct Energy Use, chemical industry model

Total material consumption is calculated using the material consumption per unit, product purchase and any recycled materials from the production or end-of-life processes.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit} - \text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} - \text{delay material recycling and reuse}$$

The product purchase, as a proxy for production, and the material consumption per unit finds the total consumption of virgin materials. However, not all materials used in the process are new and thus, the recycled materials are subtracted from the total as they are already factored in for previous years.

Table 33. Parameters used for the material consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Material consumption per unit BAU	1.04 ton/product	(Cheremisinoff, 1995)
Material consumption per unit CBBE	2023=100%; 2030=30%,2050=40% efficiency increase	
Energy consumption per unit BAU	0.00018 TJ/ton	(umweltbundesamt, 2017)
Energy Consumption per unit CBBE	2023=0.00018; 2030=0.00015; 2050=0.00013	
Energy carbon intensity BAU	8.25e-011 tonCO ₂ e/TJ	(Innovation Fund, 2021)

Energy carbon intensity CBBE	2023=8.25e-011; 2030=8.25e-011;2050=8.25e-011	
Share of materials that is waste	75%	(wbcSD chemicals, 2015)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	10%	
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=30%; 2050=50%	

6.3 Recycling and Reuse

Chemical waste and disposed chemical products are directed into the waste and recycling structure, which determines the waste's destination—whether it is reused, recycled, or sent to landfill. Material flows within this structure are governed by rates controlling the inflows and outflows with values under different scenarios outlined in Table 34.

The flow of “products resold and reused” drives domestic reuse, as the percentage resold domestically is reintroduced into product purchases. Products that are dismantled contribute to reduced material consumption, as the chemical reactants can be reused. Finally, materials destined for landfills are either incinerated or left in landfills. The stock of landfills is also impacted by production waste.

The equation calculates the quantity of materials or products that end up in landfills by subtracting the diverted materials from the total waste collected. This includes both the products dismantled for recycling and reuse, as well as those resold and reused without dismantling. The equation quantifies the effectiveness of waste diversion efforts within the system, providing insights into the proportion of materials that are successfully diverted from landfills through recycling, reuse, or resale initiatives. There is a MAX function in the landfill outflow to negate the possibility of it becoming negative and thus, reverting direction.

$$\text{materials (products) landfilled} = \text{product waste collection} - (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} + \text{products resold and reused})$$

The values for the parameters used to calibrate the waste structure can be found in Table 34.

Table 34. Parameters used for the recycling model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	60%	

Share of products collected CBBE	2023=60%;2030=80%;2050=100%	
Fraction resold and reused BAU	1.92%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	2023=1.92%;2030=20%;2050=50%	
Fraction of sorted chemicals sold domestically BAU	10%	(Kerstens & Bessembinders, 2020)
Fraction of sorted chemicals sold domestically CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=10%; 2050=20%	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	16%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	2023=16%; 2030=30%; 2050= 50%	
Share of Materials to incineration	25%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)

6.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The model tracks downstream employment such as the employment per recycling material etc. The equations are as follows:

$$\text{employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This formulation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton of X. All values for the different types of employment can be found in Table 35.

Table 35. Parameters used for the employment model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	0.00157486	(Eurostat, 2024)
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit collected and sorted	x	
Employment per unit recycled	x	
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit of waste landfilled	x	
Employment per unit of water consumed	x	
Employment per unit of energy consumed	x	
Employment per unit of waste incinerated	x	

6.5 Energy Consumption

The chemical industry in the Netherlands mainly consumes carbon-intensive fossil fuels for its production. The model structure accounts for this by using the energy intensities for the year 2022 and endogenous material consumption. The energy intensity values are shown in Table 36.

The fuel cost structure derives its equation from the 2022 price of energy and energy consumption to find the annual energy costs. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Causal tree for Total Energy Efficiency Investments, chemical industry model

The industry emission is the product of the endogenous energy consumption per energy type and the associated emission factor.

$$\text{Total CO2e emissions in tons} = (\text{fuel electricity emissions} + \text{fuel natural gas emissions} + \text{heat emissions} + \text{non renewable waste emissions} + \text{oil and petroleum emissions}) / \text{kg to ton}$$

The equation sums up the emissions from various sources, including electricity generation, fuel combustion, heating processes, and waste disposal, and then converts the total emissions from kilograms to tons. It provides a comprehensive measure of the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the industry processes.

Table 36. Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.00242654 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Heat Intensity	0.00175332 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	0.000468198 GWH/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum	0.00371134TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Nonrenewable waste intensity	2e-009 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

6.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price with the data selected as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in

Table 37. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating the same values are used for both prices.

Table 37. Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	1.3076e-006 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Electricity Price	1.32444e-007 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Heat Price	1.32444e-007 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Oil and Petroleum Price	2.00454e-005 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Nonrenewable waste price	0.0002412 Euro/TJ	(Koldenhof, 2023)

6.7 Material Costs

The costs of materials are contingent upon the input materials utilized. Given that the model assesses the chemical industry at an aggregate level, the cost of materials is averaged to euros per ton of chemicals produced. However, the cost of materials would vary if the policy's share of recycled chemicals increased. The following equation was utilized to compute the cost of materials, considering the proportion of recycled fibres used.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Annual Industry Cost for Materials} = & \\ & (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} * \text{Cost of Recycled Fibers}) \\ & + (\text{Cost of Input Materials} * \text{material consumption}) \end{aligned}$$

The parameters used for the equation can be found in Table 38.

Table 38. Material costs used in the chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Cost per ton of recycled materials	x	
Cost per ton of materials	x	

6.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of chemical purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for biobased production. The module considers the value addition from purchases, including reused chemicals, but does not disaggregate between the two.

Figure 17: Cause tree for Value addition in the chemical sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (cefic, 2023; Eurostat, 2023b; ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020; UN Population Division, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$Value\ addition\ intensity = \frac{Value\ addition_t}{Production_t}$$

The forecast for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the chemical value addition, this means 1.63% growth annually from 2028 onwards. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top of it from the literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature data ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future biobased value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of the Netherlands, and thus, the chemicals sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 5% (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Value addition conventional and biobased for the Netherland's chemical industry

The GDP of the chemical industry is calculated by summing the value addition, purchases, and the biobased share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the biobased value addition, we consider the share of production that is biobased along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both biobased and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of chemical purchases, conventional value addition, and the biobased shares of both textile purchases and value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of biobased and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\text{real value added new purchases chemicals industry} = ((\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin product} * (1 - \text{share of textile products manufactured using biobased products})) + (\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin biobased material} * (\text{share of textile products manufactured using biobased products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}$$

Since the textile GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real chemical GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value are not double counted.

Figure 19: Use tree for real GDP textile industry

7 DOCUMENTATION OF THE GREEN ECONOMY MODEL (GEM)

The following paragraphs provide an overview of the model and more detailed documentation is available in Bassi et al. (Bassi, Garrido, Harsono, & Pallaske, 2024).

The Green Economy Model (GEM) is a System Thinking based, System Dynamics macro, dynamic, integrated assessment representation of the socio-economy, and the natural capital that supports it, at the country level (Bassi, 2015; Pallaske, Bassi, Garrido, & Guzzetti, 2023).

GEM is designed to inform policymaking towards sustainable development. It allows to forecast and assess the outcomes of various policies and investments in relation to medium- and long-term national development targets. By offering a systemic approach, GEM forecasts the outcomes of action and inaction across sectors, actors, dimensions of development and over time. Further, GEM enables the formulation of policies and investment packages that result in a more inclusive, robust, and resilient outlook for the country. At the same time, by means of co-creation, GEM supports the creation of a better understanding of the co-benefits associated with sustainable policies and investments, including on climate action, under different climate scenarios.

Figure 20 presents the generalized underlying structure of GEM. Figure 21 presents instead a sub-system diagram of the model. The former shows how four key capitals (built, social, human and natural) are interconnected, and how they contribute to shaping future trends across social, economic and environmental indicators. Specifically, feedback loops can be identified that are reinforcing (R), in all areas pertaining to economic growth and social development. These are driven by investments and knowledge creation, and enabled by the availability of natural capital, which, if not properly managed, can constrain economic growth (hence the balancing loops -(B)-identified in the diagram). Policies can be implemented to promote sustainable consumption and production, to decouple economic growth from resource use (also through education and behavioural change), to mitigate the exploitation of natural capital and generate stronger and more resilient green growth.

GEM has been applied to more than 50 countries and was designed to include all key sectors that are relevant for future development, for instance in the context of low-carbon development (HMIT, 2021; BAPPENAS, 2021) and green recovery packages (UNEP, 2020). These include, among others: population, food demand and supply, land use and land cover, economic activity (via the use of national accounts), employment, access to health care, education, energy demand and supply, air emissions, water pollution, and climate trends. The model also provides an economic valuation for several externalities, including GHG emissions (social cost of carbon), air pollution, wastewater, waste, traffic-related impacts (e.g. accidents, noise), the opportunity cost of water (from savings in the agriculture sector) and biodiversity.

Figure 20. Overview of GEM, built on (Bassi, 2015).

GEM is built using the System Dynamics (SD) methodology, serving primarily as a *knowledge integrator*. SD is a form of computer simulation modelling designed to facilitate a comprehensive approach to development planning in the medium to long term (Meadows, 1980; Randers, 1980; Richardson & Pugh, 1981; Forrester, 2002). SD operates by simulating differential equations with “*what if*” scenarios, explicitly represents stocks and flows (critical to estimate climate change impacts on infrastructure, and how such impacts accumulate over time to affect economic productivity, among other indicators), can integrate optimisation and econometrics and support model coupling (e.g. in conjunction with spatially explicit models, sectoral models for energy and the economy).

The purpose of using SD for the development and application of GEM is not to make precise predictions of the future, nor to optimize performance; rather, GEM applications are used to inform policy formulation, forecasting policy outcomes (both desirable and undesirable) and leading to the creation of a resilient and well-balanced strategy (Roberts, Andersen, Deal, Garet, & Shaffer, 1983; Probst & Bassi, 2014). Such approach is consistent with the thinking framework of policymakers, who weigh *sets* of outcomes on the basis of political, technical and institutional preferences in choosing from among policy packages.

All GEM applications include four key capitals (physical, human, social and natural) as interconnected via the explicit representation of feedback loops (reinforcing or balancing)¹.

¹ In a reinforcing loop, a change in one direction is compounded by more change. Under a reinforcing loop, policies or shocks that move a variable in one direction transmit through the system in a way that leads to further increases in such variable over time. For

Policies can be implemented to strengthen growth (reinforcing loops, e.g. investments in physical capital accumulate capital stock, which, other things equal, increases output potential, production, aggregate demand, including investment, further increasing, capital and output); or curb change (e.g. by strengthening balancing loops). In the context of climate action, we generally find that transition investments directly stimulate new growth, while investments in climate resilience reduce costs and free up resources, thereby enabling new growth indirectly.

Among the many feedback relationships represented by GEM, there are two that are worth highlighting, considering how central they are for explaining the connectedness of climate, environmental and socio-economic outcomes, which is, in turn, central for the design of robust development policies. The first one refers to impacts on what mainstream models refer to as Total Factor Productivity (TFP). TFP in the model is impacted by technology, infrastructure (e.g. the road network and access to electricity), energy productivity (i.e. considering the cost of energy as a ratio of GDP), air pollution, weather (e.g. temperature) and extreme weather events. As a result, investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy, to cite two examples both reduce energy consumption and spending (possibly resulting in higher GDP), and reduce air pollution (also possibly resulting in higher GDP, but via a different channel). The second one refers to a feedback loop that governs linkages between climate, environment (including policies) and the socio-economy. This feedback loop considers the availability of natural resources, and the impacts of land cover change on ecosystem service provisioning, which goes on to affect economic activity, as well as access to natural resources. These dynamics are represented via the use of feedback loops in the model, resulting in circular relations that may highlight the simultaneous emergence of short-term benefits and medium-term challenges, or vice versa, depending on the scenarios simulated.

example, money in a savings account generates interest, which increases the balance in the savings account and earns more interest. Balancing loops, in contrast, counter change in one direction with change in the opposite direction.

Figure 21. Sub-system diagram presenting the key sectoral components of GEM.

7.1 Population

The population module provides an overview of the development of total population, births and deaths over time. The population module contains the stock of the population, which is affected by the three flows births, migration and deaths. The stock of population changes based on the integration of its three flows:

$$Population_{t+1} = Population_t + birthst_0 + migration_t - deathst_0$$

The number of births depends on the total fertility rate and the stock level of the population. Births are calculated based on the following equation:

$$\text{Births} = \text{Population} * \text{POPULATION GROWTH RATE}(\text{Time})$$

The historical population growth rate is hereby obtained from national statistics, and the forecast is calibrated to match the population forecast provided by the United Nations (UN Population Division, 2022).

The migration rate is calibrated to match the historical development of the population and is assumed zero in the future. In the Honduras model, migration is a bi-flow, which means that it can increase or decrease the total population depending on whether it is positive or negative.

The number of deaths depends on the stock level of the population and the average life expectancy. The total population is divided by the average life expectancy to obtain the annual number of deaths. In the current version of the model, life expectancy was obtained from the United Nations Population Division (2022).

$$\text{Deaths} = \text{Population} / \text{AVERAGE LIFE EXPECTANCY TABLE}(\text{Time})$$

7.2 Household accounts

The household account module serves for the calculation of nominal GDP, disposable income and private consumption, savings and investment. It provides information concerning the development of these variables over time and allows for the assessment of policy impacts on household-specific key indicators.

Table 39. Overview of data sources for the household accounts module

Variable	Type
Nominal production (GDP)	Time series
Disposable income	Time series
Private consumption	Time series
Private investment	Time series
Nominal exports	Time series
Nominal imports	Time series

The household module contains household investment and consumption and provides an indication of the real disposable household income. Household revenues are hereby calculated as the sum of nominal GDP, interest on domestic debt, private current transfers and subsidies and transfers.

$$\text{Household revenues} = \text{interest on domestic debt} + \text{private current transfers} + \text{subsidies and transfers} + \text{nominal production}$$

Total disposable income is calculated as household revenues minus government domestic revenues. Disposable income is used for the calculation of private savings and consumption, and real disposable income per capita. Real disposable income per capita is calculated by dividing disposable income by the total population and the GDP deflator. The relative value of per capita real disposable income, current real disposable income per capita divided by its initial value, affects the propensity to consume and hence private consumption and private savings.

$$\text{propensity to consume} = \text{INITIAL PROPENSITY TO CONSUME}(\text{Time}) * \text{relative pc real disposable income} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF PROPENSITY TO CONSUME TO INCOME} * \text{covid impact on propensity to consume}$$

In addition to the relative real disposable income, COVID-19 impacts on the propensity to consume are implemented. The impacts of COVID-19 on the propensity to consume are based on COVID-19 employment impacts and elasticity.

$$\text{COVID impact on propensity to consume} = \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{COVID19 SWITCH}=1 : \text{AND: DURATION OF COVID IMPACTS TABLE}(\text{Time}) > 0, \text{average covid impact on employment} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF PRIVATE CONSUMPTION TO COVID}, 1)$$

The IF THEN ELSE function allows for activating the impacts of COVID-19 in the simulations. If the COVID-19 switch has a value of “1” (= active) and capital impacts of COVID-19 are active (variable “duration of covid impacts table”), the model will use COVID-19 employment impacts and the elasticity of private consumption to estimate the impact on the propensity to consume. If the switch has a value of “0”, the variable takes a value of “1” (neutral) and no COVID-19 impacts on propensity to consume are simulated.

The propensity to consume and disposable income is multiplied to calculate total private consumption. Private savings are calculated as the difference between disposable income and private consumption.

$$\text{Private savings} = \text{disposable income} - \text{private consumption}$$

Private investments are determined based on private savings, the share of private savings for private investment and capital, corrected for monetary flows related to government financing, whereby the latter is based on historical data.

$$\text{private savings for private investment} = \text{private savings} * \text{share of savings invested} - \text{government domestic financing}$$

Nominal consumption and nominal investment are calculated as the sum of government and private consumption and government and private investments respectively. Figure 22 provides an overview of the variables used for calculating nominal consumption and Figure 23 shows the variables used for calculating nominal investment.

Figure 22: Causes tree nominal consumption.

Figure 23: Causes tree nominal investment

The causes trees above illustrate that GEM also provides the feature of simulating government recovery packages for addressing COVID-19 impacts, by allowing additional investments to be simulated. If the COVID-19 recovery switch has a value of “1” (=policy active), the model will use a different time series for calculating government consumption compared to the BAU. This change allows to keep government consumption constant and increase government investment temporarily for the duration of the recovery actions. The above highlights that both nominal consumption and investment are affected by COVID-19 impacts.

7.3 Government accounts

The government accounts module provides an overview of government revenues, investments and debt. It allows for analyzing different public spending strategies and is used as the entry point for the simulation of a government stimulus post-COVID-19. Key indicators of the government accounts module and their respective sources are presented in Table 40.

Table 40. Overview of data sources for the government accounts module

Variable	Type
Government revenues	Time series
Government investment	Time series
Desired government deficit	Time series

Public debt	Time series
Interest on public debt	Time series
Government revenues	Time series

The government accounts module captures government revenues and grants and provides information on total government consumption and investment. Total government revenue is the sum of government domestic revenue and revenues from grants, both calculated as a share of nominal GDP (named nominal production in the model). The causes tree in Figure 24 summarizes the variables used to calculate total government revenues.

Figure 24: Causes tree total government revenue

The sum of total government revenue and government domestic financing constitutes the government budget. Government financing is defined as total government revenues multiplied by the desired government deficit, a time series function estimated based on historical data. As illustrated in the uses tree in Figure 25, the government budget is used to calculate the government budget after interest, non-development expenditure and development expenditure.

Figure 25: Uses tree government budget

The government budget after interest is calculated by deducting interest payments on public debt from the government budget. The budget excluding interest serves for the calculation of government consumption and government investment, using the share of government consumption over total expenditure. Government consumption is calculated by multiplying the share of government consumption over total expenditure by the budget excluding interest; government

investment is calculated by multiplying the budget excluding interest by one minus the share of government consumption over total expenditure, as illustrated by the equation below.

$$\text{government investment} = \text{government budget after interest} * (1 - \text{share of government consumption over total expenditure})$$

Non-development expenditure is the sum of interest on public debt and the share of the government budget used for administrative purposes.

$$\text{Non-development expenditure} = \text{interests on public debt} + \text{government budget} * \frac{\text{ADMINISTRATIVE EXPENDITURE AS SHARE OF BUDGET}}{\text{GDP Deflator}}$$

Development expenditure, which is used to calculate investments in health care, education and resource efficiency, is equal to the government budget corrected for non-development expenditure.

$$\text{development expenditure} = \text{MAX}(\text{government budget} - \text{non development expenditure}, 0)$$

A MAX function is used to avoid that development expenditure becomes smaller than zero, which would be equivalent to negative investment.

Investments in health care, education and resource efficiency are calculated by multiplying government development expenditure by the desired share of development expenditure invested in health care, education and resource efficiency respectively. The desired investment shares for health care and education are calibrated to ensure that the resulting investments are consistent with historical data.

$$\text{education expenditure} = \text{development expenditure} * \text{desired share of development expenditure for education}$$

7.4 Land use

The land use module provides information about aggregate land use and land use change over time. This module allows for assessing the impacts of development policies on land use and potential conversions of land resulting from their implementation. The land use module contains four stocks; forest land, agriculture land, settlement land and fallow land. Five flows are used to capture land use change over time. Stocks and the respective flows are illustrated in Table 41.

Table 41. Overview of stocks and flows in the land use module

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Forest land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fallow to forest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest to settlement Forest to agriculture
Agriculture land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest to agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture to fallow

Settlement land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest to settlement • Fallow to settlement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None
Fallow land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture to fallow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fallow to forest • Fallow to settlement

Agriculture land, and changes therein, are caused by land conversion for agriculture (forest to agriculture and fallow to agriculture) and the depreciation of agriculture land (agriculture to fallow). The flow of forest to agriculture is calculated by the equation below.

$$\text{Forest to agriculture} = \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in agriculture land} + \text{agriculture to fallow}, \text{Forest Land} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FOREST LAND})$$

A MIN function is used to ensure that land conversion is constrained if the desired change in agriculture exceeds the available forest area for conversion. The desired change in agriculture hereby indicates the difference between established and required agricultural land. The desired change in agriculture is the gap between desired agricultural land and currently established agricultural land. The desired amount of agricultural land is hereby based on the total population and per capita agriculture land multiplier.

$$\text{desired agriculture land} = \text{Population} * \text{desired agriculture land per capita}$$

The stock of settlement land has two inflows, assuming that forest and fallow land can be converted for the expansion of urban areas. Land conversion for settlement land is based on the desired settlement land, which is calculated by multiplying the population by the desired settlement land per capita. The equations are formulated based on the assumption that, as long as there is fallow land available for conversion, there will be no deforestation for establishing settlement land. The following equation is used for calculating the conversion of fallow to settlement land.

$$\text{Fallow to settlement} = \text{MAX}(0, \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in settlement land}, \text{Fallow Land} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FALLOW LAND}))$$

A MIN and a MAX function are used for the calculation of land conversion from fallow to settlement land. The MIN function ensures that the conversion of land from settlement land cannot exceed the amount of fallow land currently available (same as for the conversion of forest land for agriculture). In case of the event that the stock of settlement land is higher than the desired settlement land (indicating a negative desired land conversion for settlement land), there would be a flow from settlement land back to fallow land. The MAX function ensures that the current level of settlement land is maintained in case of such an event.

In the case of land conversion for settlement land, forest land serves as a buffer. This means that the conversion of forest to settlement land is only assumed if the amount of fallow land is below the amount required for converting the desired amount.

$$\text{Forest to settlement} = \text{MAX}(0, \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in settlement land} - \text{waste to settlement}, \text{Forest} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FOREST LAND}))$$

As in the case of fallow to settlement, a MIN and a MAX function are used to ensure that land conversion takes place based on land available, and that no reduction of settlement land occurs.

The stock of forest land changes based on land conversion for agriculture and settlement land and the regeneration of forests from fallow land. The outflows of the forest stock, forest to settlement and forest to agriculture, are documented above. The regeneration of forests is the sum of forest regeneration, calculated by dividing the stock of fallow land by the average forest regeneration time, and annual reforestation. The equation for the inflow to the forest stock is presented below.

$$\text{Fallow to forest} = \text{Fallow Land} / \text{AVERAGE FOREST REGENERATION TIME}$$

7.5 Carbon stock and emissions from land

The carbon stock module provides information about Ethiopia’s carbon stock and changes therein caused by land conversion. The module is used to assess how policy-induced land use changes affect the country’s carbon stock and land emissions.

Table 42. Overview of data sources for the carbon stock module

Name of variable	Type	Source for estimation
Carbon factor forest land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor settlement land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor agriculture land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor fallow land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)

Carbon stocks are calculated by multiplying the four different land-use stocks by a respective carbon factor. The sum of the four carbon stocks represents the total carbon stock. Figure 26 shows the variables used for the calculation of the total carbon stock.

Figure 26: Causes tree total carbon stock

Annual emissions from land are calculated based on land conversion. The calculations are based on the five flows described in the documentation of the land use module and the carbon factors applied to the four land use stocks. The causes tree in Figure 27 shows the variables used for the calculation of the net change in carbon stock from land conversion and the CO₂e emissions from land.

Figure 27: Causes tree CO₂e emissions from land

To estimate the change in carbon stock caused by land use change, the model calculates the net change in total CO₂ that is caused by land conversion. This is done by calculating the difference in carbon stock from the land use class subject to conversion and the target land use class. The equation below illustrates the calculation of the change in carbon stock occurring if forest land is converted to agricultural land.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to forest} = \\ & \text{forest to agriculture} * \text{adjusted carbon factor agriculture for land use calculations} \\ & - \text{forest to agriculture} * \text{adjusted carbon factor forest for land use calculations} \end{aligned}$$

The same approach is applied to calculate the changes in carbon stock for the other four flows. The net change in carbon stock is then calculated as the sum of the individual changes in carbon stock caused by the conversion of land.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{net change in carbon stock from land conversion} = \\ & \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to fallow} + \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to forest} \\ & + \text{change in carbon stock from fallow to forest} + \text{change in carbon stock from forest to settlement} \\ & + \text{change in carbon stock from fallow to settlement} \end{aligned}$$

7.6 Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The Gross Domestic Product module provides information about the development of total real GDP, the three sectoral GDPs (agriculture, industry and services) and their respective shares in total real GDP. This module allows for assessing policy impacts on total real GDP and real GDP growth as well as potential changes in the economy, indicated by changes in sectoral contributions to real GDP.

The agriculture, industry and services modules serve for the calculation of the GDP of the sectors that have not been disaggregated for the analysis of the economy. All three sectors are described in this section. While the same structural building blocks are used to represent industry and services in the model, the agriculture module is more disaggregated and hence described in a separate section.

7.6.1 Agriculture GDP

This module provides information about agriculture productivity and employment over time. Key indicators are agriculture's real GDP and its growth rate, employment in agriculture and indicated investment in agriculture. The module allows for assessing the impacts of development policies on agriculture GDP and employment, such as for example the reduction of losses during the transport of goods to market.

Agriculture's real GDP is calculated based on the real agriculture production rate and a value-added per ton of produce multiplier. The variable "real agriculture production rate" accounts for pre-harvest losses and loss of produce during transport to market (see crop production section).

$$\text{Real GDP agriculture} = \text{real agriculture production rate} * \text{VALUE ADDED PER TON PRODUCED}(\text{Time})$$

The growth rate of agriculture's real GDP is calculated using a TREND function, which estimates the change in agriculture's real GDP on an annual basis.

$$\text{real gdp growth rate agriculture} = \text{TREND}(\text{real gdp agriculture}, "1 \text{ YEAR DELAY TIME}", \text{INITIAL REAL GDP GROWTH RATE AGRICULTURE})$$

Employment in agriculture is calculated based on total agricultural land. The equation below is used to calculate employment in agriculture.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{employment agriculture} = & \text{land used for crop production} * \text{EMPLOYMENT PER HECTARE OF AGRICULTURE LAND TABLE}(\text{Time}) \\ & * (1 - \text{share of agriculture sustainable}) + \text{land used for crop production} \\ & * \text{EMPLOYMENT PER HECTARE OF AGRICULTURE LAND TABLE}(\text{Time}) * \text{share of agriculture sustainable} \\ & * (1 + \text{ADDITIONAL EMPLOYMENT FROM SUSTAINABLE CROPLAND}) \end{aligned}$$

This formulation indicates that agriculture employment is the sum of employment in conventional and sustainable agriculture. The underlying assumption for this equation is that sustainable agriculture has a higher labour intensity per hectare, which is accounted for by using the share of sustainable cropland and a multiplier.

7.6.2 Industry and Services GDP

For the industry and services modules, the supply-side approach is used. Throughout this section, the 'industry module' will serve as an example to illustrate equations and variables that are used to represent the residual sectors. Table 43 provides an overview of the data sources used for calibrating real GDP, employment and total factor productivity.

Table 43. Overview of data sources for the industry and services GDP module

Variable	Type
Total employment	Time series
Industry real GDP	Time series

Services real GDP	Time series
Employment in industry	Time series
Employment in services	Time series
Total employment	Time series

Capital, labour and productivity are used to calculate the performance of the residual sectors. The stock of Industry Capital changes based on the following equation

$$Industry\ Capital_{t+1} = Industry\ Capital_{t0} + investment\ industry_{t0} - depreciation_{t0} - loss\ of\ industry\ capital\ due\ to\ floods_{t0}$$

Investment in industry is defined as nominal investment industry, which is calculated by multiplying total nominal investment (the sum of private and government investment) by the share invested in industry. The formulation is based on the assumption that the industry will invest in capital to maintain or extend production.

The depreciation of industry capital is calculated by dividing the current Industry Capital by the average lifetime of industry capital. The depreciation captures machinery that reaches the end of its lifetime or facilities that are outdated. Relative industry capital, an indicator of how much Industry Capital has changed compared to the beginning of the simulation, is calculated by dividing the stock level of Industry Capital by its initial value.

In addition, the model simulates the impacts of COVID-19 on productive capital by inducing an additional capital outflow between 2020 and 2023 (assuming 3 waves of the pandemic). The equation for the depreciation of industry capital is presented below.

$$depreciation\ of\ industry\ capital = Capital\ Industry / average\ capital\ life * covid\ effect\ on\ capital\ industry$$

Employment in the industry is calculated by multiplying Industry Capital by the labour intensity of the industry sector, an employment factor indicating the employment generated per unit of capital, and the COVID-19 impact on employment.

$$employment\ industry = Capital\ Industry * real\ labor\ intensity\ industry * covid19\ effect\ on\ industry\ employment$$

The labour intensity of the industrial sector is affected by the relative labour cost, which affects sectoral employment depending on the cost of labour. If unemployment increases, the cost of labour declines and allows for increased hiring to take place. A decrease in unemployment on the other hand would increase labor costs and curb job creation.

$$real\ labor\ intensity\ industry = Labor\ Intensity\ Industry / Actual\ Relative\ Labor\ Cost$$

Relative employment in the industry sector is calculated by dividing the employment in the industry by its initial value.

Industry GDP represents the sector’s economic performance. It is calculated by multiplying initial GDP industry by production multipliers that account for employment and capital (with a respective elasticity using the Cobb-Douglas formulation) and total factor productivity. The following formulation is used for the calculation of real industry GDP:

$$\text{Real GDP industry} = \text{initial GDP industry} * \text{relative capital}^{\text{capital elasticity industry}} * \text{relative employment level industry}^{\text{labor elasticity}} * \text{total factor productivity industry}$$

Figure 28 presents a causes tree that depicts the variables used for calculating real industry GDP and determining the total factor productivity of the industry sector. Total factor productivity depends on the development of the energy bill, health care, adult literacy, technology, wastewater treatment and CO₂e emissions. The following equation is used for calculating Relative production in the industry sector.

$$\text{Total factor productivity industry} = \text{effect of technology on capital productivity} * \text{effect of emissions on total factor productivity} * \text{effect of energy bill on industry tfp} * \text{effect of roads on total factor productivity} * \text{effect of habitat quality on productivity} * \text{effect of WBG T on labor productivity}$$

Figure 28: Causes tree real GDP industry

Table 44 provides the equations used to determine the effects constituting total factor productivity with their respective equation.

Table 44. Documentation of effects constituting total factor productivity industry

Effect name	Effect equation
effect of technology	Tech ^ elasticity of industry tfp to technology

effect of emissions	DELAY3I (relative total CO _{2e} emissions from energy [^] elasticity of TFP to CO _{2e} emissions, "1 year delay time", 1)
effect of energy bill	DELAY3I (relative energy bill as share of GDP [^] elasticity of energy bill on industry TFP, "1 year delay time", 1)
effect of roads on TFP	DELAY3 (relative km of roads [^] elasticity of industry tfp to roads, "2 year delay time")
Effect of habitat quality	IF THEN ELSE (Time>2020,indicated effect of habitat quality on productivity/effect of habitat quality on productivity in 2020,1)
effect of Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)	effect of extreme temperature on labor productivity [^] elasticity of labor productivity to WBGT

7.7 Employment and Technology

This module provides an overview of both sectoral and total employment and the development of technology over time. It allows for the assessment of employment impacts of policy interventions and for changing trends in technological development underlying the analysis.

Table 45. Overview of data sources for the employment and technology module

Name of variable	Type
Employment in agriculture	Time series
Employment in industry	Time series
Employment in services	Time series
Annual change in technology	Constant
Labor force participation rate	Time series
Average annual salary	Time series

Total employment is calculated as the sum of sectoral employment from agriculture, industry and services. Figure 29 shows the variables used for estimating total employment using a causes tree. The equations used for estimating sectoral employment are described in the previous section.

Figure 29: Causes tree total employment

Total employment and the labour force are used to calculate the unemployment rate. The labour force is hereby calculated by multiplying the total population by the labour force participation rate. The unemployment rate is calculated using a MAX function to avoid the variable from taking negative values.

$$\text{Unemployment rate} = \text{MAX}(1 - \text{total employment} / \text{labor force}, 0)$$

Technology, or ‘Tech’ in the model, is used to affect total factor productivity, and is modelled as a stock with an initial value of one (“1”) and an annual growth rate. It is an index that increases steadily over time, representing improvements in machinery as well as automation of processes.

7.8 Energy demand

The model projects national energy consumption by sector and source, from 2000 to 2050. Energy consumption is then multiplied by GHG emission factors to obtain total national emissions from the use of energy.

The main structural assumptions of the model are (see Figure 30):

- Final energy consumption is estimated considering (1) indicated demand (including the effect of GDP, population and energy efficiency); (2) the price effect; and (3) the substitution effect. Items (1) and (2) are used to estimate *demand for energy services*.
- The potential for fuel substitution is represented by the ratio of an energy price over the national weighted average energy price. This implies that an energy source will become more attractive if its price increases less than others when subsidies are removed.
- It is assumed that price effects require a 1-year delay to influence energy consumption.

One of the main drivers of the model is energy price, which can be modified in two ways: (1) by setting baseline medium to longer-term trends (which is an endogenous calculation for electricity) and (2) by removing fossil fuel subsidies. The removal of subsidies increases energy prices, which lowers energy demand in two possible ways: energy is becoming more expensive and consumption is reduced to offset the growth in expenditure, and, if energy services are required, the use of (previously) subsidized fossil fuels declines and consumption of now comparatively cheaper fuels increase. GHG emissions are affected by both the reduction of energy consumption and the change in fuel mix, and the model analyzes these effects separately. As a result, the model allows to estimate the impact of fossil fuel subsidy removal on GHG emissions and compare such reduction to other possible intervention options (e.g. investments and/or mandates on energy efficiency and renewable energy). Emission reductions can also be estimated as a result of the reallocation of subsidy savings, such as through investments in RE and EE.

Figure 30: Energy demand estimation sketch.

Several variables and equations are used to estimate energy flows (which are measured in terajoule per year, TJ/year) and emissions (which are measured in tons per year, ton/year).

To begin with, indicated sectoral energy demand (*coal* is presented as an example) is calculated using the initial value for 2000, multiplying it by relative GDP and relative population (both | energy efficiency (also indexed to 2000)). The use of subscripts, ‘sector’ in the example provided below, allows for calculating energy demand for the residential, commercial, industrial, and transport sectors within the same variable.

$$\text{Indicated Coal Demand}[\text{sector}] = (\text{INITIAL COAL DEMAND TABLE}[\text{sector}] * \text{Relative GDP}^{\text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO GDP}[\text{sector}]} * \text{Relative Population}^{\text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO POPULATION}}) / \text{Relative Energy Efficiency}$$

The price effect is then added, simply taking the indicated demand (presented above) and multiplying it by relative energy price (indexed to 2000) and raised to the power of a price elasticity.

The removal of fossil fuel subsidies is reflected in energy price changes. When subsidies are removed, it is assumed that energy prices increase for all sectors (unless it is known that subsidies are allocated to specific users). Users can indicate the extent to which subsidies are removed and the timeline (e.g. full removal, linearly, by 2030).

$$\text{"Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} = \text{Indicated Coal Demand[sector]} * \text{Relative Coal Price} ^ \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE[sector]}$$

Next, the substitution effect is considered. The formulation is the same as the one used for incorporating the price effect, but a delay of 1 year is used to represent the lag existing between price changes and demand (or consumption) changes.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{"Coal Demand (With Substitution Effect)"[sector]} = \\ \text{DELAY N(("Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} * \text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} ^ \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE[sector]}), \text{ TIME TO ADAPT DEMAND TO PRICE CHANGES, ("Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} * \text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} ^ \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE[sector]}), 3) \end{aligned}$$

The potential for substitution from one energy source to another, due to price changes (e.g. as a result of fossil fuel subsidy removal), is incorporated here by using the ratio of energy source price (e.g. coal) over the average energy price of the country (estimated as a weighted average of all energy prices). This ratio is also indexed, to ensure consistency with the use of elasticities.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} = \\ \text{DELAY N}((\text{Relative Coal Price}/\text{Relative Weighted Average Energy Price}), 1, 1, 1) \end{aligned}$$

Indicated energy demand (including the price effect) is used to estimate the total indicated energy demand (which is also demand for energy services), which is the total energy that has to be guaranteed at the country level. The potential for substitution is instead used to estimate the actual share of energy consumption by source. As a result, a normalisation is performed by multiplying the total indicated energy demand by the shares obtained from the inclusion of the substitution effect.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Normalized Coal Demand[sector]} = \\ \text{Total Indicated Country Energy Demand} * \text{Normalized Coal Share Of Energy Demand[sector]} \end{aligned}$$

7.9 Energy bill

The energy bill provides an overview of the country-level energy cost by type of fuel and the relation between energy cost and total real GDP. The latter is used to estimate energy cost impacts on total factor productivity. The causes tree in Figure 31 presents the variables that are used to calculate the energy bill.

Figure 31: Causes tree Energy bill

In all cases, the cost of energy is calculated using the normalized country energy demand by fuel, the price of energy and, where required, a conversion factor to align units of measure. The equation used for calculating the country-level cost of petroleum is described below.

$$\text{cost of petroleum} = \text{total country normalized petroleum demand} * \text{petroleum price} * \text{conversion tj to a liter of petroleum}$$

The energy bill, calculated as the sum of costs across all fuel categories, is converted from USD to local currency units (LCU) using the exchange rate. To calculate the impacts of energy cost on total factor productivity for industry and services, the energy bill as a share of nominal GDP is calculated.

$$\text{energy bill as share of gdp} = \text{energy bill in lcu} / \text{nominal production}$$

The relative energy bill as a share of GDP, an index calculated by dividing the current energy bill as a share of GDP by its initial value in the year 2000, is used to calibrate the impacts of energy cost on industry and services TFP. The uses tree for the relative energy bill as a share of GDP is presented in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Uses tree Relative energy bill as a share of GDP

7.10 Power generation capacity

The power generation module captures the demand for electricity, transmission losses and required and current power generation capacity. The module uses the total normalized electricity demand as input to assess electricity generation by technology and forecast future capacity requirements. It further provides information about total electricity generation, both by

technology and system-wide, and the shares of generation by technology. The power generation module uses the subscript [power generation technology], which allows to use of the same structural components to estimate capacity, generation and cost for the 14 technologies presented in Table 46.

Table 46. Power generation technologies considered in GEM

Power generation technologies	
Diesel and fuel oil	Hydropower (large scale)
Cogeneration	Hydropower (small scale)
Gas turbine	Solar power (utility scale)
Steam coal	Solar PV (rooftop)
Nuclear	Wind (onshore)
Biomass	Wind (offshore)
Geothermal	Waste generation

Power generation capacity is represented using two stocks: *Power Generation Capacity Under Construction* and *Power Generation Capacity*. The installation and usage of power generation capacity is driven by the desired electricity generation rate, which considers both imports and transmission losses.

$$\text{desired electricity generation} = \text{electricity demand in mwh} * (1 + \text{TRANSMISSION LOSSES TABLE}(\text{Time}))$$

The desired electricity generation serves as input for the calculation of the desired electricity generation by technology, which is calculated by multiplying the total desired generation by the shares of generation satisfied by the respective technology.

$$\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{desired electricity generation} * \text{electricity generation shares peak demand}[\text{power generation technology}]$$

Considering the load factor and the number of hours per year, the desired electricity generation by technology is used to calculate the required electricity generation capacity for each technology.

$$\text{required electricity generation capacity by technology} = (\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] / \text{hours per year} / \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}])$$

The power generation capacity gap calculates the capacity generation gap by comparing the required power generation capacity with the currently installed capacity. The capacity gap for all technologies considered is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{power generation capacity gap}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{required electricity generation capacity by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{Power Generation Capacity Under Construction}[\text{power generation technology}]$$

The required electricity generation capacity is compared to the current power generation capacity and power generation capacity under construction to determine whether there is a capacity gap.

The stock of power generation capacity under construction is changed by the construction rate and the completion rate. The construction rate increases the stock level and is calculated by dividing the power generation capacity gap by the time to process capacity orders. The completion rate is an outflow of power generation capacity under construction and an inflow to power generation capacity. The completion rate is defined as a fixed order delay based on the construction rate and the construction time of all technologies, based on the assumption that capacity becomes functional once the construction is completed. Power generation capacity is increased by the completion rate, and decreased by decommissioning, whereby decommissioning is calculated as a fixed delay of the completion rate and the capacity lifetime, based on the assumption that capacity depreciates after a fixed lifetime.

An additional flow captures the retirement of capacity. This flow is established to ensure that the currently installed power generation capacity is equal to the active amount of capacity required based on the desired electricity generation shares. The retirement of capacity is estimated based on the power generation potential if capacity would be utilized at full capacity (given the respective load factors) and the desired electricity generation by technology. The difference between the two represents the excess power generation with currently installed capacity.

$$\text{excess power generation with current capacity} [\text{power generation technology}] = \text{MAX}(0, \text{potential power generation with full capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}])$$

Dividing the excess power generation by technology by the load factor and the number of hours per year yields the amount of capacity to be phased out to match the current generation capacity given the desired shares of electricity generation by technology.

$$\text{capacity phase out to match required capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{excess power generation with current capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] / \text{LOAD FACTOR TIMES BASELINE}[\text{power generation technology}] / \text{hours per year}$$

Capacity phase-out divided by the time to phase out capacity constitutes the flow retirement of power generation capacity.

Electricity generation is calculated based on the power generation capacity, the load factor, and the hours per year. It represents the total amount of electricity that is produced. The following equation is used to calculate the electricity generation for all capacity types.

$$\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{MAX}(\text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] < \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}], \text{MIN}(\text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}], \text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}])$$

$$\text{technology}), \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}], 0)$$

The MIN function is used to ensure that only the required amount of electricity is produced, hence avoiding overproduction. It compares the current generation potential, by technology, to the desired electricity generation, by technology. If the potential generation is higher, the MIN function ensures that the technology in question does not produce more electricity than demanded. The MAX function is used to avoid electricity production can take negative values in case of integration errors that may occur through the retirement of capacity.

The total electricity generation rate represents the sum of electricity generation from all types of capacity and is calculated by using a SUM function to add up the electricity production of all technology subscripts. The share of renewable generation is calculated as the sum of renewable generation divided by total generation across all technologies, as represented by the following equation

$$\text{share of renewable generation} = \text{ZIDZ}(\text{SUM}(\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{all renewables!}]), \text{SUM}(\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{power generation technology!}])))$$

7.11 Employment from power generation

The employment module captures the employment that is generated through the construction and maintenance of energy-generating capacity. It allows for observing the impact that different energy pathways have on the total employment of the energy sector. Furthermore, it also captures the employment that is generated through the extraction of fossil fuels.

Table 47 provides an overview of key variables of the module, and lists the reports and documents that are used for the parameterisation of the module.

Table 47. Key variables and sources in the Employment module

Name of variable	Type
O&M employment per MW of thermal capacity	Time series
O&M employment per MW of hydropower capacity	Time series
O&M employment per MW of RE capacity	Time series
employment per MW of thermal capacity	Time series
employment per MW of hydropower capacity	Time series
employment per MW of RE capacity	Time series

Employment from the energy sector is divided into employment from the construction of capacity and employment from the operation and maintenance of capacity. Figure 33 shows the variables that are used to calculate the employment that is generated by the energy sector. The variable electricity employment represents the sum of employment that is generated by construction and operations and maintenance per capacity type.

Figure 33: Causes tree of electricity employment

Construction employment is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{construction employment} = \text{Power Generation Capacity Under Construction[technology]} * \text{construction employment per mw of capacity[technology]} * \text{FRACTION OF CONSTRUCTION TAKING PLACE DOMESTICALLY}$$

The power generation capacity under construction is multiplied by a construction multiplier per MW of capacity and the fraction of construction taking place domestically. The fraction of local construction corrects for the manufacturing that is not generated domestically if power generation capacity is imported.

O&M employment is calculated by multiplying power generation capacity by the O&M employment per MW of capacity. The variables construction employment per mw of capacity and O&M employment per MW of capacity are time series variables that contain employment multipliers for each type of capacity.

Total O&M employment and total construction employment are the sum of the generated employment in operations and maintenance, and the construction of capacity respectively, for all capacity types. The variables total thermal and nuclear employment, total hydropower employment and total renewable employment are indicator variables that provide an overview of the number of people that are employed based on capacity types.

7.12 CO₂e emissions

The CO₂e emissions module calculates country-wide CO₂ emissions from all sectors. The module provides information about the development of CO₂e emission over time and allows for the assessment of policy impacts on CO₂e emissions per capita and the social cost of carbon.

Total annual CO₂e emissions are calculated as the sum of emissions from energy, industry (IPPU) and waste, livestock, managed soils, and land use (land use, land use change and forestry, or LULUCF). The variables underlying the calculation of total and sectoral CO₂e emissions are illustrated in the causes tree in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Causes tree total CO₂e emissions

Emissions from industry is calculated based on industry real GDP and emission intensity per unit of industry real GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{co2e emissions from industry and waste} = \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE (LOW IMPACT DEVELOPMENT POLICY SWITCH=1, real GDP industry * industry emissions per} \\
 & \text{unit of industry real GDP(Time) * (1 - LCD emission reductions from improved processes table(Time)),}
 \end{aligned}$$

IF THEN ELSE (LOW IMPACT DEVELOPMENT POLICY SWITCH=2, real GDP industry * industry emissions per unit of industry real GDP(Time) * (1 - NZE emission reductions from improved processes table(Time)), real GDP industry * industry emissions per unit of industry real GDP(Time)))

The GE reduction in industry emission intensity is a policy variable and is used to allow for the simulation of policies that would reduce emissions from industry and to assess their impacts on total CO_{2e} emissions. If the GE policy switch is active (value of “1”), the model will simulate a reduction in industry emission intensity. This reduction is a policy input and will be informed by national plans related to reducing emissions from the industrial sector.

CO_{2e} emissions from energy are calculated as the sum of emissions generated across all sectors through the use of energy (see energy demand module) but the non-energy use sector.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total co2e emissions from energy} = & \\ & (SUM(\text{coal emissions}[\text{sector excluding nonenergy use!}]) + SUM(\text{electricity emissions}[\text{sector excluding nonenergy use!}]) \\ & + SUM(\text{natural gas emissions}[\text{sector excluding nonenergy use!}]) + SUM(\text{petroleum emissions}[\text{sector excluding nonenergy use!}]) \\ & + SUM(\text{biofuels and waste emissions}[\text{sector excluding nonenergy use!}])) \end{aligned}$$

GHG emissions from livestock are calculated as the sum of CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management and N₂O emissions from manure management.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{co2e emissions from livestock} = & \\ & \text{co2e emissions from livestock ch4} + \text{co2e emissions from manure management} \end{aligned}$$

Livestock-related CH₄ and N₂O emissions as described above are converted into CO_{2e} using a conversion factor for the GHG equivalent of CH₄ and N₂O respectively.

CO_{2e} emissions from managed soils are calculated as the sum of total N₂O emissions from managed soils and CO₂ emissions from urea and limestone application.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{co2e emissions from managed soils} = & \\ & ((\text{total n2o emissions from managed soils} / \text{UNIT CORRECTION FOR N2O} * \text{N2O TO CO2}) + \text{co2 emissions from urea and limestone}) / \text{KG PER TON} \end{aligned}$$

The causes tree in Figure 35 illustrates the variables used to calculate total N₂O emissions from managed soils.

Figure 35: Causes tree total N₂O emissions from managed soils

Total annual CO_{2e} emissions serve for the calculation of the CO_{2e} emissions per capita and the country-level social cost of carbon. CO_{2e} emissions per capita are calculated by dividing total CO_{2e} emissions by population. The social cost of carbon on the country level is based on total CO_{2e} emissions and the social cost of carbon per ton of carbon emitted (Nordhaus, 2017). GEM does not assume an escalation of SCC as proposed by Nordhaus (2017), indicating that the SCC per ton of CO_{2e} emitted remains constant at USD 31 per ton throughout the simulation.

$$\text{annual social cost of carbon} = \text{total co2e emissions} * \text{SOCIAL COST OF CARBON PER TON} * \text{EXCHANGE RATE USD TO LEMPIRAS}$$

7.13 Air pollution from energy consumption and power generation

GEM estimates the occurrence of air pollutants from final domestic energy consumption and power generation. In total, GEM estimates 11 pollutants across energy sources and sectors. The emission factors were obtained from the emission factor database of the LEAP Integrated Benefits Calculator (IBC), which is publicly available². Air pollutants considered in GEM are:

- CO₂
- CO
- NO_x
- N₂O
- NMVOC
- CH₄
- PM10
- PM2.5
- Black carbon
- Organic Carbon
- Ammonia (NH₃)

Air pollutants for energy consumption and power generation are calculated separately. Air pollutants from final energy consumption are calculated by multiplying the total final energy demand (by fuel source) by a respective emission factor by type of fuel and sector. For example, pm10 emissions from biomass use, for each sector considered, are calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{pm10 emissions from biomass[sector]} = \text{normalized biofuels and waste demand[sector]} * \text{PM10 EMISSIONS PER TJ OF BIOMASS BY SECTOR[sector]} / \text{KG PER TON}$$

The same approach is used for all other fuel types (coal, petroleum, natural gas). Air pollutants from power generation are calculated by multiplying the fuel used for the generation of electricity by respective emissions per TJ of the fuel used multiplier.

$$\text{fuel use for power generation in tj[power generation technology]} = \text{fuel use per mwh by technology new[power generation technology]} * \text{electricity generation rate[power generation technology]}$$

The emission factors used for the estimation of air pollutants from energy consumption and power generation are summarized in Table 48.

² <https://leap.sei.org/default.asp?action=IBC>

Table 48. Overview of air pollution multipliers for energy consumption and power generation

Fuel type/Sector	CO2	CO	Nox	NMVOC	CH4	PM10	PM2.5	Black Carbon	Organic Carbon	N2O	NH3
	Ton/TJ	kg/TJ									
<i>Coal</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	94.6	2,610	34	484	300	490.1	440.4	72.85	196.4	0	38.74
<i>Commercial</i>	94.6	931	173	88.8	10	117	108	6.9	5.2	1.5	0.0093
<i>Industry</i>	94.6	931	173	88.8	10	117	108	6.9	5.2	1.5	0.0093
<i>Transport</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
<i>Petroleum</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	67.46	93	306	20	10	21	18	10.1	2.89	1.51	0.108
<i>Commercial</i>	74.1	130	942	50	10	96	96	40	28	0.6	0.168
<i>Industry</i>	74.1	66	513	25	3	20	20	11.2	3.6	0.6	0.154
<i>Transport</i>	69.3	5,808	644.2	741.81	33	161.64	161.64	9.27	116.38	3.2	31.03
<i>Natural gas</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	56.1	26	51	1.9	5	1.2	1.2	0.065	0.54	0.1	0.181
<i>Commercial</i>	56.1	29	74	23	5	0.78	0.78	0.03	0.26	0.942	1.214
<i>Industry</i>	56.1	29	74	23	1	0.78	0.78	0.03	0.26	0.1	1.214
<i>Transport</i>	56.1	271.7	543.48	12.14	92	0.725	0.725	0.036	0.326	2.72	N/A
<i>Biofuels and waste</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	95.6	4,753	134.6	1,654	300	512.35	409.88	51.24	178.4	134.57	53.7
<i>Commercial</i>	112	570	91	300	300	143	140	39.2	72	4	37
<i>Industry</i>	112	570	91	300	30	143	140	39.2	72	4	37
<i>Transport</i>	79.6	5,808	51	0.69	18	1.9	1.9	0.16	0	0	0

<i>Power generation (by fuel type)</i>											
<i>Fuel and diesel oil</i>	77.4	15.1	142	2.3	3	25.2	19.3	0.957	0.359	0.6	0.101
<i>Cogeneration</i>	77.4	15.1	142	2.3	3	25.2	19.3	0.957	0.359	0.6	0.101
<i>Natural gas</i>	565.1	39	89	2.6	1	0.89	0.89	0.022	0.022	0.1	1.829
<i>Coal</i>	96.1	8.7	247	1.4	1	7.9	3.2	0.083	0.167	1.5	0.012
<i>Waste incineration</i>	91.7	90	81	7.31	30	155	133	1.444	0.222	4	0.222

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ANNEX 1

This annex presents an adaptation of the policy portfolios prepared in Deliverable 4.1 for the BioTransition and BioRevolution scenario for the four industries: construction, plastics, textiles and chemicals. The policies selected from the policy portfolio in D4.1 are the ones that are specific enough and can be simulated with the industry models described in sections 3, 4, 5, and 0 of this report.

Table 49. Construction industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioTransition scenario

Year	Demand (buildings renovation)	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		<p>1. Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020).</p>		<p>1. The preparing for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>2. Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008).</p> <p>3. The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 80% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 50% (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>4. The use of primary raw material in buildings renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For</p>

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				<p>bio-based materials, maximum 90% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 75% (European Commission, 2023).</p>
2030	<p>1. At least 2% of annual energy renovation in buildings, involving these key principles: (i) energy efficiency, (ii) affordability, (iii) decarbonisation and integration of renewables, (iv) life-cycle thinking and circularity, and (v) high health and environmental standards (European Commission, 2020).</p> <p>2. double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector, and renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually (European Commission, 2021).</p>		<p>1. Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>2. climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019).</p>	

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Table 50. Construction industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioRevolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1. Improve materials productivity at 2% per year (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020).		1. Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008).
2030		<p>1. At least 2% of annual energy renovation (European Commission, 2020).</p> <p>2. (...) double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector. (...) renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>3. 5 Mt of CO₂ should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030. (25)(including vacancy management of buildings) (European Commission, 2021)</p> <p>4. Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils).</p>	<p>1. Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>2. climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019).</p>	<p>1. The preparing for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>2. The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 80% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 50% (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>3. The use of primary raw material in buildings renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 90% come from primary raw material. For non-biobased plastic in 75% (European Commission, 2023).</p>
2050		<p>1. Adapted policy goal: (...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>To about 1,5% of worldwide market in the sectors of construction, plastics and textiles</p>		<p>1. Adapted policy goal</p> <p>As many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists.</p>

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Table 51. Plastics industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioTransition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025	1. Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).	1. Improve raw materials productivity (1.5% per year) (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020).	<p>1. use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023)</p> <p>2. from 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).</p>	<p>1. member states shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018).</p> <p>2. by 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>3. by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>4. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/year (Unwelt Bundesamt, 2024).</p>
2028			1. From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).	
2030			<p>1. from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).</p> <p>2. Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum</p>	1. Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (European Environment Agency, 2022b).

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			<p>percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging:</p> <p>(a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component;</p> <p>(b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p>	<p>2. Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets:</p> <p>(c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated;</p> <p>(d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated:</p> <p>(i) 55 % of plastic;</p> <p>(ii) 30 % of wood; (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>3. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/year (Unwelt Bundesamt, 2024).</p>
2040			<p>1. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging:</p> <p>(a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p>	

Table 52. Plastics industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioRevolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025	<p>1. Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019)</p> <p>2. Annual reduction in growth of plastic: 1,5%/year (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018).</p>	<p>1. Improve raw materials productivity (2% per year) (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), 2020)</p>	<p>1. use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>2. from 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019)</p>	<p>1. member states shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018).</p> <p>2. by 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>3. by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>4. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).</p>
2028			<p>1. From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).</p>	
2030			<p>1. from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).</p> <p>2. Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major</p>	<p>1. Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 7,5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>2. Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight</p>

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			<p>component;</p> <p>(b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p>	<p>of all packaging waste generated;</p> <p>(d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated:</p> <p>(i) 60 % of plastic;</p> <p>(ii) 35 % of wood; (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p> <p>3. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).</p>
2040			<p>1. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging:</p> <p>(a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).</p>	<p>1. Mechanical recycling: 45% and chemical recycling of 15% (adapted from (Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany, 2021) & (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018))</p>
2050			<p>1. Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilisation,)</p>	

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Table 53. Textile industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioTransition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1.ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO ₂ in the non-ETS sectors (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022).		1. Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022 (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021)
2026				1.Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through 'Textile Hubs' (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2030	1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects" (European Commission, 2022). 2.to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products (European Commission, 2022).		1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects" (European Commission, 2022).	1.Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017).
2035	1.the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).			1.ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).

D4.2 - Complete Green Economy Model (GEM)

Table 54. Textile industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioRevolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1.ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO2 in the non-ETS sectors (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022).		1. Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2026				1.Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through 'Textile Hubs' (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2027			1. Adapted or added policy goal: The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%.	2. Adapted or added policy goal: 30% of resources, materials and products placed on the textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible. 3. Adapted or added policy goal: 10% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused after collection.
2030	1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (European Commission, 2022). 2.to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and		1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (European Commission, 2022). 2. Adapted or added policy goal:	1. Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycle and 20% will be sustainable textiles. 2. Adapted or added policy goal:

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	reliable way to choose eco-friendly products (European Commission, 2022).		<p>supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer)</p> <p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles.</p>	<p>50% of resources, materials and products placed on the market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.</p> <p>3. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>15% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused in the after collection.</p> <p>4. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion</p>
2035	<p>1.the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).</p> <p>2. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain</p>		<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>The aim is to halve the ecological footprint of the textile industry with regard to emissions, water usage, chemicals and microplastics</p>	<p>5.ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).</p> <p>6.Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017)</p>
2050			<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector</p>	<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>Full circular textile material flows</p>

D4.2 - Complete Green Economy Model (GEM)

Table 55. Chemical industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioTransition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2030		<p>1.Reduction of 5 Mt of CO2 emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>3. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).</p> <p>1. 20% of the carbon used should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030 (European Commission, 2021).</p>	<p>2.Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p>	
2050		<p>2. 0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020).</p> <p>3. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 75% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).</p>		<p>1.In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are 80% circular (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p> <p>1. To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised.(...) (European Commission, 2020).</p>

D4.2 - Complete Green Economy Model (GEM)

Table 56. Chemical industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, BioRevolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2030		<p>1. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).</p> <p>2.Reduction of 5 Mt of CO2 emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>At least 30% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030</p>	<p>2.Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p>	
2040				<p>1. To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised (European Commission, 2020).</p>
2045		<p>1.0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020).</p>		
2050		<p>1.reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 75% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p> <p>1. Adapted or added policy goal:</p> <p>At least 40% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources 2050.</p>		<p>1.In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p>

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